

TOPICAL REVIEW

Radio-Frequency Power Amplifiers in MRI Systems: A Comprehensive Review

MERT KARADEMİR^{1,2}, OĞUZHAN KIZILBEY^{1,2}, AND BAKİ KARABÖCE¹

¹TÜBİTAK National Metrology Institute (TÜBİTAK UME), 41470 Kocaeli, Türkiye

²Faculty of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Istanbul Technical University, 34467 Istanbul, Türkiye

Corresponding author: Oğuzhan Kizilbey (oguzhan.kizilbey@tubitak.gov.tr)

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ABSTRACT The radio-frequency power amplifier (RFPA) serves as one of the critical subsystems in Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), directly influencing the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and overall image quality. This paper provides a comprehensive review of recent advancements in RFPA technology, synthesized from a systematic analysis of 21 selected studies spanning from 1.5-T clinical systems to 11.7-T ultra-high-field (UHF) research platforms. The review covers device technologies, architectures, and control/linearization methods. The review discusses the transition from silicon LDMOS architectures to wide-bandgap devices, particularly gallium nitride (GaN) and silicon carbide (SiC), which enable higher power density and improved efficiency. The review highlights the shift toward modular design strategies, such as 15-kW and 64-kW arrays, and the integration of sophisticated digital control mechanisms including Digital Pre-Distortion, Frequency-Offset Cartesian Feedback, and order-reduced state-space controllers for gradient subsystems. In addition, several studies investigate switch-mode power amplifiers and delta-sigma modulation as enabling technologies for portable, low-field MRI scanners. By evaluating diverse power combining topologies, ranging from coaxial Wilkinson to lumped-element Gysel designs, and robust safety interlock protocols, this paper delineates the technical trade-offs between linearity, thermal management, and physical footprint. The review concludes with a comparative summary of published RFPA designs and their reported performance.

INDEX TERMS High field MRI, low field MRI, magnetic resonance imaging, radio frequency power amplifier.

I. INTRODUCTION

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is one of the most important tools of modern diagnostic medicine, largely because it provides an unparalleled level of soft-tissue contrast and spatial resolution without the safety risks inherent to ionizing radiation. While traditional modalities like X-ray or Computed Tomography (CT) depend on high-frequency photon absorption, MRI functions on a fundamentally different physical plane, exploiting the principles of Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) to probe the electromagnetic characteristics of biological tissues. By carefully

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manipulating the magnetic moments of nuclei, most commonly hydrogen protons, within a powerful static magnetic field, clinicians can non-invasively visualize complex pathophysiology. This capability is critical for everything from the early-stage detection of subtle lesions to the long-term, longitudinal monitoring of how a patient responds to a specific treatment protocol [1], [2].

At the heart of this imaging process lies the radio frequency (RF) transmit chain, where the Radio Frequency Power Amplifier (RFPA) serves as the primary engine. The fundamental mandate of the RFPA is to drive the transmit coil with enough power to establish a homogeneous magnetic field, which is the mechanism required to excite the nuclei into resonance. Achieving this is a significant engineering

feat; the RFPA is tasked with conditioning and amplifying relatively low-power pulse sequences into high-power waveforms that often-hit kilowatt-level peaks. All of this must happen while the system maintains incredibly strict timing and spectral purity, as any deviation at this stage can cascade through the rest of the signal chain [3], [4], [5], [6].

To better understand why RFPA imperfections are critical in MRI, a simple envelope-domain representation of the transmit signal chain is introduced. In MRI, the goal is not only to increase signal power, but also to preserve the amplitude and phase of the excitation waveform while delivering sufficient power to the transmit coil. Even small RFPA-induced deviations can alter the intended excitation profile, affecting flip-angle accuracy, slice selectivity, spatial encoding, and ultimately image quality. In this context, a compact mathematical description helps explain how amplifier nonlinearity leads to excitation errors and highlights the importance of RFPA behavior in MRI.

For this purpose, a simplified nonlinear amplifier model is used to provide physical insight rather than a complete device-level description. Although it does not capture all practical effects, such as memory effects, thermal dynamics, load modulation, or broadband matching limitations, it is sufficient to illustrate how amplitude and phase distortions degrade MRI pulse fidelity. Thus, the following analysis should be viewed as a conceptual framework for understanding the sensitivity of MRI excitation to RFPA nonidealities, rather than as a comprehensive behavioral model of a practical amplifier.

The fundamental basis of selective magnetic resonance excitation relies on the precise synthesis of radiofrequency pulses. Mathematically, the intended amplification transmit signal can be defined as a complex baseband envelope, denoted as $u(t)$, which can be seen in (1). This waveform is inherently characterized by two dynamic components: its time-varying amplitude envelope, $A(t)$ and its instantaneous phase trajectory, $\varphi(t)$. Therefore, the accuracy of the final MRI image is strictly dependent on preserving both the morphological integrity of $A(t)$ and the temporal precision of $\varphi(t)$ throughout the transmission chain.

$$u(t) = A(t)e^{j\Phi(t)} \quad (1)$$

In a perfectly linear regime, the RFPA acts as an ideal scalar multiplier. Under these conditions, the amplified output, $y_{id}(t)$, is strictly proportional to the input sequence $u(t)$ via a constant complex gain factor, G_0 , as shown in (2).

$$y_{id}(t) = G_0 u(t) \quad (2)$$

However, practical high-power RFPAs utilizing physical semiconductor devices exhibit inherent nonlinear transfer characteristics, particularly when driven near saturation to maximize power efficiency. A highly illustrative first-order model defines the distorted output, $y(t)$, in (3).

$$y(t) = (a_1 + a_3|u(t)|^2)u(t)e^{jk|u(t)|^2} \quad (3)$$

The linear gain coefficient is represented by a_1 , while the term $a_3|u(t)|^2$ parameterizes the cubic AM-AM distortion, and the exponential term governed by the coefficient k models the AM-PM conversion. By expanding the aforementioned model, the explicit degradation of the transmitted MRI waveform becomes analytically apparent. The magnitude of the output envelope, $|y(t)|$, is mathematically corrupted by the cubic nonlinearity shown in (4).

$$|y(t)| \approx a_1 A(t) + a_3 A^3(t) \quad (4)$$

This $a_3 A^3(t)$ term predictably causes gain compression at the peak of the excitation pulse. In the frequency domain, this temporal distortion destroys the rectangular spectral profile required for sharp slice-selection, leading to out-of-band excitation and degraded spatial resolution. Simultaneously, the output phase trajectory is altered to (5):

$$\angle y(t) = \Phi(t) + kA^2(t) \quad (5)$$

This expression reveals that the transmitted phase is no longer solely the desired $\varphi(t)$, but includes an amplitude-dependent rotational error, $kA^2(t)$. Because MRI relies fundamentally on phase coherence for spatial encoding and multi-channel signal combination, this amplifier-induced phase jitter directly translates into ghosting artifacts and localized signal voids.

Ultimately, this framework proves that even if an MRI pulse is synthesized at the baseband level, the intrinsic nonlinearities of the RFPA will corrupt the transmission.

Furthermore, as the industry pushes toward higher magnetic field strengths, such as 7T and beyond, or adopts different architectures that we'll review. The performance requirements for the RFPA have become exponentially more demanding. System designers are now forced to balance extreme linearity and wide bandwidth against the need for high efficiency and thermal stability in increasingly dense hardware environments [7].

Ultimately, bridging the gap between an ideal RF pulse and the actual, measured output of a power amplifier is the central challenge for modern system designers. This review seeks to provide a comprehensive analysis of the state of RF power amplification within the specific context of MRI technology. We delve into the fundamental parameters that dictate pulse fidelity and offer a detailed categorization of the diverse architectural strategies used to implement RFPAs in contemporary scanners. Our goal is to clarify the technological trade-offs and mitigation techniques like digital pre-distortion or feed-forward linearization, that are required to maintain signal integrity in the increasingly complex and high-field environments of modern medicine [8], [9].

II. REVIEW STRATEGY

In this study, we examined RFPAs, one of the most important parts of MRI systems, widely used in imaging technology. We reviewed many different papers and examined how each study progressed and worked. Our study, which examines these papers, consists of different separate sections for each paper in the "Overview of Methods" section. First, we added

a section examining the narrative and methods of the study we reviewed. In this section, we generally discussed the working methods of MRIs and the methods used to design gradient amplifiers. The main points of the studies are presented in this section. Later, we added some experimental results based on figures from the study. In this section, we also added the proposed topologies and discussed how the study was conducted using them. In the final part, we discussed the results of these studies. We examined whether the targeted results were achieved or whether there were areas for improvement. By the end of this review, we aim to assist researchers who wish to conduct research in the MRI and RF power amplifier fields. Our goal is to provide easy access to different topologies and their results from a single resource.

III. OVERVIEW OF METHODS

A. 8KW NON-MAGNETIC RF POWER AMPLIFIER OF 5T HUMAN BODY MAGNETIC RESONANCE

Achieving whole-body UHF imaging requires robust power-drive capabilities to optimize the excitation of radio frequency coils, which necessitates a high-efficiency RF transmission chain to mitigate significant signal losses. To address these requirements, authors propose 8 kW non-magnetic RF power amplifier (RFPA) specifically for 5T whole-body MRI applications [10]. By utilizing a non-magnetic architecture, the RFPA can be situated directly within the scanning room, a configuration that significantly shortens transmission distances and improves overall efficiency. This system employs a multi-stage amplification topology based on high-power MOSFETs, integrating a magnetic-planar balun and a lumped-distributed power combiner to reach a peak output power of 8 kW. Operational precision is maintained through a dual directional coupler and feedback control loop design, which facilitate gain nonlinearity correction and real-time status monitoring. As medical diagnostics increasingly demand higher signal-to-noise ratios, greater resolutions, and faster imaging speeds [11], the clinical necessity for UHF MRI continues to grow. While 7T and higher field systems remain constrained by specific absorption rate limitations and B1 field inhomogeneities, 5T MRI remains the predominant platform for research into ultra-high field whole-body imaging.

Established research models and analysis methods [12], [13], [14] indicate that higher field strengths require greater RFPA output to sufficiently drive RF coils, achieve target field intensities, and mitigate both standing wave effects and dielectric artifacts. A significant challenge arises as power increases: traditional installations place the RFPA in a separate device room, where long-distance cable runs to the scanning room typically incur transmission losses exceeding 30%. This configuration substantially reduces power utilization. By placing a non-magnetic RFPA directly in the magnet room, transmission distances are minimized and efficiency is improved. To meet the power requirements of 5T whole-body imaging while addressing these transmission losses,

a non-magnetic 8 kW RFPA featuring an integrated feedback and monitoring system was developed. This design achieves non-magnetic characteristics by utilizing a planar balun instead of a standard magnetic transformer. Real-time monitoring of reflected and output power is managed via a dual directional coupler and feedback control loop, which replace traditional magnetized circulators. Structurally, the amplifier employs a three-stage, four-channel configuration, with a collector-distributor power combiner delivering the 8-kW peak power necessary for 5T MRI applications.

The proposed RFPA utilizes a non-magnetic topology capable of delivering an 8-kW output, as detailed in the architectural schematic of Fig. 1. Within this framework, the pre-amplifier and driver stages function to elevate low-level RF signals to the specific drive requirements of the final power stage. Following the driver stage, the signals are split equally among four discrete power amplifier channels via a two-stage Wilkinson power splitter. These parallel signals are subsequently aggregated by a power combiner to produce the final high-power output. To ensure system stability and operational oversight, a directional coupler is integrated to provide synchronous low-power samples, facilitating the real-time monitoring of both output and reflected power levels [10].

To achieve the requisite 8 kW output, the system employs a driver stage that partitions power into four parallel amplification paths via a high-isolation 3 dB Wilkinson power divider. By utilizing a lumped π equivalent circuit instead of standard microstrip transmission lines, the design significantly reduces the overall circuit footprint. The final stage leverages an adjustable Wilkinson power combiner specifically engineered to withstand high power densities while mitigating combining losses caused by inter-channel amplitude and phase variances. As illustrated in Fig. 2, this combiner replaces traditional, bulky inductors with a hybrid microstrip and compact inductor configuration. This architecture allows for the precise tuning of L and C values to synchronize the channels, ensuring maximum power summation and system efficiency for 5T MRI applications.

To validate its performance, a high-power characterization platform was established, integrating a vector network analyzer, an MXG N5182B RF signal source, a Rohde & Schwarz FSV3 spectrum analyzer, and a Shanghai Hua Xiang high-power attenuator, as detailed in Fig. 3. Measurements conducted on this platform confirm that the amplifier achieves a peak output power of 69 dBm (8 kW) at a center frequency of 210.78 MHz. The system exhibits robust linearity across a 40 dB dynamic range, with a 1 dB compression point (P_{1dB}) of 69.17 dBm. Furthermore, the design maintains high gain stability, with flatness variations confined within ± 0.25 dB.

Authors state that through iterative simulation and hardware debugging, a high-power, non-magnetic RFPA was successfully implemented for 5T MRI applications. The design utilizes a planar non-magnetic balun for precise impedance transformation, while a microstrip directional coupler replaces conventional magnetized circulators. This

FIGURE 1. High power non-magnetic RF power amplifier structure diagram [10].

FIGURE 2. High power combiner structure [10].

FIGURE 3. Overall system test results [10].

substitution facilitates real-time monitoring of output and reflected signals without the interference of magnetic materials. To maintain operational consistency across the four channels, the adjustable power combiner limits amplitude and phase variances to under 0.2 dB and 2° , respectively. Experimental characterization demonstrates a peak output power of 8 kW and a gain flatness of ± 0.25 dB over a 40 dB dynamic range. By achieving a fully non-magnetic architecture, the amplifier can be situated directly within the scanning room to minimize transmission losses.

B. 2-KW HIGH-EFFICIENCY AND BROADBAND GAN LINEAR RF POWER AMPLIFIER FOR MULTINUCLEAR MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING

This study introduces a high-efficiency, 2-kW broadband gallium nitride (GaN) linear power amplifier optimized for 5.0T systems. Multinuclear MRI is clinically vital for

diagnosing and monitoring major diseases; while ^1H -MRI provides anatomical detail, deuterium (^2H) metabolic imaging, sodium (^{23}Na) MRI, and phosphorus (^{31}P) MRI offer unique physiological insights, such as detecting tumor cell necrosis or quantifying tissue sodium in stroke and Alzheimer's patients [15]. The RF power amplifier (RFPA) is a critical component of the transmit module, as it provides the high-power pulses necessary to excite nuclei at specific resonance frequencies. For 5.0T multinuclear applications, the RFPA must satisfy four stringent criteria: broadband operation (30–300 MHz) to support multiple nuclei, high linearity to prevent image distortion, high efficiency to ensure system stability and reduce cooling demands, and kilowatt-level output to maintain an adequate signal-to-noise ratio [16].

Conventional MRI systems frequently lack support for multinuclear imaging, largely due to the limitations of traditional silicon-based RF power amplifiers (RFPAs). These legacy systems are often constrained by narrowband operation and suboptimal efficiency. As operating frequencies broaden, the parasitic capacitance and inductance inherent in silicon technologies intensify, complicating the maintenance of linearity and efficiency at higher frequencies. Furthermore, elevated output power levels in these systems often trigger gain compression and intermodulation distortion during frequency transitions [3]. Various architectures have been explored to overcome these bottlenecks. For instance, Class D amplifiers utilizing CMCD topologies—integrated with Kahn-technique modulation and current feedback—have been proposed to enhance efficiency in parallel transmission systems [4]. However, these designs often introduce trade-offs in linearity and bandwidth that are incompatible with multinuclear requirements. Other approaches, such as push-pull Class AB structures using VDMOS, have achieved 1-kW broadband amplification but remain limited in peak power and efficiency. Adaptive optical control RFPAs have also been investigated for X-nuclei MRI, yet their integration into transmit coils adds significant complexity and potential reliability issues, particularly regarding consistent tuning across diverse nuclei. Consequently, existing research continues to face challenges in simultaneously optimizing linearity, broadband impedance matching, efficiency, and operational stability.

This study introduces the development of an innovative 2-kW high-efficiency broadband linear RFPA designed for 5.0T multinuclear MRI systems, focusing on maintaining high-power delivery and operational stability across a 30–300 MHz bandwidth. The architecture leverages a multi-objective load-pull optimization analysis to identify precise load impedances for GaN transistors, ensuring superior gain flatness and maximized power efficiency throughout the operating range. To address the complexities of multi-channel synthesis, the design incorporates compensation inductor technology within the power combiner to enhance isolation and minimize phase and amplitude variances. Furthermore, an adaptive frequency-based pre-compensation linearization method was implemented to ensure signal integrity

FIGURE 4. Overall block diagram [16].

across a 40 dB dynamic range without compromising system efficiency. The development process transitioned from validated large-signal GaN modeling to the implementation of multi-section distributed matching networks, ultimately synthesizing the output of four GaN transistors to achieve a peak output of 2 kW. Experimental results confirm that this design maintains efficiencies exceeding 60% while restricting gain and phase variations to within ± 1 dB and 10° , respectively, providing a robust hardware solution for high-field multinuclear imaging applications [16].

The architecture of the proposed broadband GaN power amplifier, depicted in Fig. 4, integrates several critical functional modules: a pre-amplification driver stage, a high-power stage utilizing GaN HEMTs, a pre-compensation linearization unit, a wideband power combiner, and a gate-voltage modulation module for UNBLANK signal generation. Across the 30–300 MHz operational band, the system achieves a total gain of approximately 63 dB. In the driver stage, the RF input is initially boosted by 24 dB via an AWB688 pre-amplifier, followed by a 20 dB amplification from a UG25-600 F medium-power transistor configured in a Class A push-pull topology. The final power stage synthesizes the output of four SK1090RVPS GaN transistors through a wideband combiner to reach peak power levels. To maintain gain flatness and inter-stage stability across the decade bandwidth, a π type lumped-element equalizer is employed. This equalizer utilizes absorption filtering and even-mode analysis to counteract low-frequency gain surges, ensuring consistent amplitude-frequency characteristics by gradually reducing attenuation as the frequency increases. To mitigate the thermal challenges inherent in high-intensity pulsed MRI operations, which can otherwise degrade semiconductor conductivity and imaging quality, the system utilizes a liquid cooling infrastructure. High-power components are bonded to a cooling plate using thermally conductive silicone grease, with cooling pipelines positioned directly beneath the devices for maximum heat transfer efficiency [17], [18].

Experimental characterization of the GaN power amplifier was conducted using a Keysight N9020B spectrum analyzer

FIGURE 5. (a) Peak output power at different frequencies. (b) Temperature of the cooling plate with 2-kW output power [16].

FIGURE 6. Efficiency and gain flatness of the broadband GaN power amplifier in the frequency range of 30–300 MHz [16].

to verify peak power delivery. As illustrated in Fig. 5(a), the system consistently achieved a 2-kW output across the target frequency spectrum. Under a pulsed operational mode with a 20 ms pulse width, the measured power droop remained below 0.3 dB, indicating robust output stability. Thermal performance was evaluated by monitoring the cooling plate temperature adjacent to the power transistors; at a 2-kW output level with a 20% duty cycle, the operating temperature was successfully maintained below 60°C , as shown in Fig. 5(b). Efficiency metrics at the 2-kW threshold were derived by measuring the drain current with a Tektronix TCP A300 current probe and validating the output power with a Rohde & Schwarz NRP2 power meter. With the RF pulse parameters set to a 10 ms width and a 10% duty cycle, the amplifier demonstrated efficiencies of 70.3% at 32.37 MHz, 68.1% at 55.74 MHz, 64.8% at 85.34 MHz, and 63.7% at 210.78 MHz. These results can be seen in Fig. 6. Throughout the full decade bandwidth, gain variation was confined within ± 2 dB, confirming the suitability of the broadband design for multinuclear MRI [19], [20], [21], [22].

Authors claim that GaN HEMT technology represents a superior architecture for achieving high-efficiency, broadband linear RF power amplification in multinuclear MRI systems. Notably, this work marks the first implementation of a GaN-based broadband high-power RFPA within a multinuclear MRI framework. The system utilizes a high-performance four-way power combiner characterized by low insertion and return losses, extended bandwidth, and high isolation to synthesize the outputs of four GaN modules into a single 2-kW delivery path. To maintain signal integrity,

an adaptive pre-compensation linearization technique based on real-time frequency recognition was integrated. Measurements confirm that the 2-kW amplifier maintains excellent linearity and efficiency across the 30–300 MHz band, with specific efficiencies of 70.3%, 68.1%, 64.8, and 63.7%. Furthermore, within a 40 dB dynamic range at peak power, phase and gain variations were limited to less than 10° and ± 0.9 dB, respectively. The practical utility of the design was successfully demonstrated through ^1H and ^2H MR spectroscopy and imaging within an upgraded 5.0T MRI system.

C. A LOW-COST AND COMPACT HIGH-FREQUENCY GALLIUM NITRIDE GRADIENT POWER AMPLIFIER FOR LOW-FIELD MRI

To reduce the entry cost and footprint of low-field MRI systems, Bolding et al [23], explore a gradient power amplifier designed to leverage the falling costs and high-performance metrics of Gallium Nitride (GaN) power transistors and high-speed digital logic. The primary objective is to achieve high operational efficiency and responsiveness in driving gradient coils while significantly reducing the financial burden associated with conventional amplification systems. Conventional solutions, such as the AE Techron 7224, deliver substantial power but are characterized by significant weight (20.9 kg), large physical dimensions, and high costs [24]. This research proposes a switching H-bridge GPA design based on GaN technology. The prototype was evaluated for power output and responsiveness using a load that simulates the gradient coils found in head and extremity low-field scanners. Beyond power delivery, the study includes a detailed analysis of the operational noise spectra.

The power conversion stage utilizes an H-bridge configuration comprising two modular half-bridge GaN units, as illustrated in the schematic of Fig. 7. Each module integrates two transistors with their respective drivers and peripheral circuitry. This modular approach facilitates streamlined fabrication and repair while allowing for parallel design iterations. The system employs pulse-width modulation (PWM) to regulate the switching duty cycle, and the entire assembly is housed on a compact PCB that includes control signal conditioning and an integrated current-sense resistor for closed-loop current regulation. The H-bridge operates by alternating between two primary switching states to apply the supply voltage across the output filter in opposing directions. In the first state, the upper-right and lower-left transistors are biased; in the second, the upper-left and lower-right transistors conduct. A key feature of this design is the use of hard switching with zero dead-time, enabled by high-precision timing and high-performance GaN drivers. While dead-time is traditionally required to prevent shoot-through the efficiency and rapid response of the GaN FETs keep these losses negligible, allowing for a simplified control architecture. The amplifier is capable of delivering ± 60 V and over 15 A DC, with switching frequencies exceeding 2 MHz. Due to its high efficiency, the module maintains an operating

FIGURE 7. The amplifier comprises two half-bridge modules in an H-bridge configuration, driving the load through an LC low-pass filter and a current sense resistor [23].

temperature near 25°C under full duty cycle without the need for forced-air or liquid cooling. Given that most gradient applications do not require frequencies above 100 kHz, a compact output filter is implemented. This configuration effectively suppresses megahertz-range switching ripple while maintaining a broad 150 kHz control bandwidth [25], [26].

Experimental validation of the gradient power amplifier was performed in two phases: an initial characterization of standalone operational specifications, followed by integrated testing with a control system to evaluate practical performance. For the standalone phase, a 1Ω resistive load was utilized to approximate the real impedance of small-scale gradient coils across a broad frequency range. These tests confirmed that the design adheres to its power handling and thermal specifications; specifically, the module sustained a continuous 15 A DC output at an ambient temperature without requiring external cooling or forced-air dissipation. To verify suitability for imaging applications, the prototype was subjected to a high-performance trapezoidal gradient waveform. As illustrated in Fig. 8, the driver achieved a peak current of 13 A with a measured slew rate of 32,500 A/s. The test platform employed an inductor simulating the $225\ \mu\text{H}$, 0.4Ω z-gradient coil developed by O'Reilly et al. [27], which features an efficiency of 1.02 mT/m/A. Based on these parameters, the proposed GPA provides an effective drive strength exceeding 15 mT/m and a slew rate surpassing 32 T/m/s, meeting the requirements for high-performance low-field MRI.

The expansion of magnetic resonance imaging into diverse healthcare environments, particularly in resource-constrained regions, depends heavily on the development of high-performance yet cost-effective hardware. By leveraging recent innovations in power electronics, this study demonstrates that advanced semiconductor devices and high-speed logic can simplify gradient power amplifier architectures while maintaining rigorous performance standards. The proposed GPA utilizes the high switching speeds and superior efficiency of Gallium Nitride (GaN) technology to minimize the reliance on bulky peripheral components. This high-frequency operation enables the use of significantly smaller output filters and reduces the thermal management

FIGURE 8. Slew test with trapezoidal waveform [23].

burden. While switch-mode topologies often introduce noise concerns, these are mitigated in this design by shifting the switching frequency and its higher-order harmonics well beyond the imaging bands of low-field systems typically operating below 10 MHz. By utilizing GaN transistors to achieve high switching frequencies, the design circumvents the filter-size and noise artifacts traditionally associated with switch-mode amplifiers. Validation tests demonstrate a bidirectional current output of up to 15 A at 24 V. The amplifier achieves a slew rate of 32 T/m/s without the need for external cooling, offering a scalable path toward making high-quality MRI more accessible globally.

D. A HIGH DUTY-CYCLE, MULTI-CHANNEL, POWER AMPLIFIER FOR HIGH-RESOLUTION RADIOFREQUENCY ENCODED MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING

The objective of this study was to develop a dedicated dual-channel radiofrequency power amplifier (RFPA) specifically designed for Transmit Array Spatial Encoding (TRASE) at 0.22 T [28]. Conventional MRI systems rely on B₀ field gradients for spatial encoding; however, the high cost, three-phase power requirements, and necessary water-cooling infrastructure of these systems often preclude their use in low-cost or portable MRI applications. Authors claim that TRASE offers a viable alternative by utilizing the phase gradients of the RF field itself for spatial encoding, thereby eliminating the need for complex B₀ gradient hardware. Despite removing the B₀ gradient burden, TRASE imposes unique and rigorous demands on the RFPA architecture. The technique requires the generation of a rapid

FIGURE 9. A main RF amplifier (second stage) circuit modified from [28].

TABLE 1. Requirements for the RF power amplifier used in trase [28].

Specification	1D TRASE requirement
Peak RF power output	≥ 1 kW
Number of channels	≥ 2
RF duty cycle	≥ 50%
Blanking noise level (BNL)	≤ -171 dBm/Hz
Pulse-to-rising/falling edge time	≤ 10 μs
RF rise/fall transition time	≤ 5 μs
Minimum pulse length	≤ 100 μs
Harmonics strength at 1 kW	< -12 dBc
Class	AB
Total gain	+60

sequence of high-power RF pulses to populate k-space within the T₂ decay window. To optimize performance, an RFPA must support a high duty cycle, peak output power, and ultra-fast switching characteristics. You can examine the requirements in Table 1. Additionally, maintaining minimal blanking noise is essential for signal integrity. This study details the construction of a dual-channel prototype using discrete commercial components, validated through bench testing and integration with a 0.22 T MRI system utilizing a twisted solenoid and saddle RF coil configuration [28].

The proposed dual-channel RF power amplifier utilizes a two-stage architecture to achieve a total gain of +60 dB at 9.27 MHz, specifically optimized for the unique pulse requirements of TRASE MRI. The initial stage employs a Class-A pre-amplifier to provide +33 dB of gain with high linearity, ensuring minimal signal distortion before reaching the power stage [29]. The second stage leverages an NXP BLF188xr transistor, originally designed for high-power broadcast applications [30], which was significantly modified for pulsed MRI operation via a custom-designed blanking circuit and gating controller. To satisfy the rapid switching transitions necessary for TRASE, the bias network was optimized by removing parallel capacitors to eliminate RC integrating delays, effectively reducing PRE and PFE while accepting a marginal trade-off in the blanking noise floor. The main RF amplifier is shown in Fig. 9.

Purchase et al. introduces a two-stage, Class-AB, push-pull RF amplifier specifically engineered for TRASE MRI.

TABLE 2. Tested parameters of the constructed trase RF power amplifier obtained with the MRI console [28].

Sr. No.	Parameter
Peak RF output power	1 kW per channel
Number of channels	2
RF duty cycle per channel	0-50% ^a
Blanking noise level (BNL)	-172±1.1 dBm/Hz
RF rise transition duration (RRT)	2 μs
RF fall transition duration (RFT)	1 μs
Pulse-to-rising edge time (PRE)	7.5 ^b μs
Pulse-to-falling edge time (PFE)	15 ^b μs
Minimum pulse length	60 ^c μs
Third harmonic strength at 1 kW	-10 dBc
1,2,4-6 Harmonic strength at 1 kW	< 30 dBc
Class	AB
Total gain	~+60

The architecture, adapted from amateur radio communication, was validated both through bench testing and integration with a 0.22 T MRI system. Results (Table 2) confirm that the design meets the rigorous operational demands of the TRASE technique marking a significant improvement over commercial alternatives that are traditionally constrained by lower duty cycles and slower switching speeds. Although the current prototype was tested at 9.27 MHz, the broadband nature of the BLF188xr power stage (1.3–54 MHz) allows for adaptation to other low-field MRI environments between 0.11 and 1.27 T. While the amplifier demonstrates superior pulse stability, future iterations will address the reduction of the relatively high third harmonic strength through the integration of dedicated duplexers to filter RF output [31].

E. HIGH EFFICIENCY RADIOFREQUENCY POWER AMPLIFIER MODULE FOR PARALLEL TRANSMIT ARRAYS AT 3 TESLA

This study details the development of a high-density, in-bore radiofrequency power amplifier (RFP) module, optimized for efficiency and power density within 3 Tesla parallel transmit (pTX) arrays. To overcome the efficiency limitations of traditional linear amplifiers, this architecture leverages a hybrid combination of Current-Mode Class D (CMCD), Class S, and Class E topologies. These stages are constructed using enhancement-mode gallium nitride-on-silicon (eGaN-on-Si) field-effect transistors, which offer superior switching characteristics compared to conventional silicon devices. The system implements an Envelope Elimination and Restoration (EER) technique to achieve precise amplitude modulation while maintaining high efficiency across a broad operational envelope [4].

Switch-mode RFPA's operate between the cutoff and Ohmic regions. These systems prioritize low on-state resistance ($R_{DS(on)}$) and rapid switching speeds. Consequently, many LDMOS devices optimized for linear operation are ill-suited for high-efficiency switch-mode applications. A comparative analysis of enhancement-mode Gallium Nitride FETs and traditional LDMOS transistors reveals significant advantages for switch-mode designs. Table 3 shows

TABLE 3. Properties of select LDMOS and eGaN FETs [4].

	EPC2007	EPC2012C	EPC2038	MRF136	MRF6V2010NR1
$V_{DSS}(V)$	100	200	100	65	110
$R_{DS(on)}(\Omega)$	0.03	0.1	2.8	1.4	4.0
$R_{DS} * C_{OSS}$ ($\Omega * F$)	3.5E-12	6.4E-12	4.8E-12	38E-12	29E-12
Area (mm ²)	1.9	1.6	0.81	400	121

the comparison of several performance parameters of eGaN FETs. The superiority of eGaN technology is most evident in the product of $R_{DS(on)}C_{OSS}$ figure of merit (FoM), which is at least six times lower than that of LDMOS devices at equivalent voltage ratings [32], [33].

The module (Fig. 10) is engineered to operate as a high-efficiency linear RF power amplifier through an “envelope elimination and restoration” technique [34], which ensures that the amplitude-modulated output remains strictly proportional to the low-power RF input. Physically, the system utilizes a stacked PCB topology to isolate sensitive signal conditioning and control logic on the bottom layer from the high-power Class S, CMCD, and Class E switching stages on the top layer. While the current prototype relies on four separate coaxial cables to deliver DC bias, the main V_S supply, and the RF reference signal, the design is inherently scalable to a single-cable configuration, which would significantly simplify the deployment of on-coil or in-bore parallel transmit (pTX) arrays.

The 3T module was designed to achieve a two-fold increase in peak output power to 125 W, while shifting the interface to support unbalanced 50Ω loads. This was accomplished by utilizing EPC2012C eGaN FETs in the CMCD stage. Furthermore, the RF output incorporates a bias tee-coupled PIN diode driver to facilitate active detuning of the RF coil. At the elevated frequencies required for 3T, the implementation of square-wave gate drives is hampered by layout parasitics; consequently, the design employs sine-wave driving for the eGaN FET gates in both the Class E pre-amplifiers and the CMCD stage which can be seen in Fig. 11. A critical design constraint for these eGaN devices is the narrow margin between the optimal 5 V gate drive and the absolute maximum V_{GS} rating. To prevent the catastrophic failure that can occur with gate overdrive the gate impedance transformers were specifically engineered to clamp the V_{GS} within safe operating limits.

The experimental characterization of the 3T in-bore module, illustrated across five iterations in Fig. 12, reveals a highly linear relationship between the RF output magnitude and the RF_{REF} power for input levels exceeding -19 dBm. Below this threshold, the output power reaches a floor caused by the Class S amplifier's minimum 10 ns on-time constraint, resulting in a total dynamic range of 36dB. The system exhibits characteristic AM-PM distortion; at lower power levels, this is attributed to gate-drive feedthrough via the parasitic reverse transfer capacitance of the eGaN FETs, while at higher power levels, the distortion stems from the

FIGURE 10. Block diagram of the module architecture. Area inside the dashed box represents contents of the power board [4].

FIGURE 11. Schematic of one half of the differential RF chain on the power board [4].

nonlinear relationship between the output capacitance and the bias voltage. Quantitative power analysis (Fig. 6(c)(d)) tracks the fundamental output power and dissipated power, while Fig. 6 (e) details the overall efficiency. The efficiency calculations account for the total DC bias power and a quiescent power consumption of 2.05W required by the module’s control circuitry.

The final prototype of this in-bore RFPA module demonstrates the practical advantages of the Current-Mode Class D topology using GaN FETs at 123.25 MHz. The system achieved a peak output power of 130 W into an unbalanced 50Ω load with a peak efficiency of 85%. This represents a significant performance leap over previous iterations, which were limited to 40 W and 80% efficiency. Despite its efficiency, the CMCD architecture faces specific control challenges, notably a 36 dB dynamic range limit imposed by the Class S gate driver’s minimum pulse width and significant AM-PM distortion driven by GaN parasitic capacitances. Additionally, phase drift caused by thermal fluctuations necessitates advanced mitigation strategies [35].

F. ACTIVE CAPACITOR VOLTAGE BALANCING CONTROL OF FLYING CAPACITOR SEVEN-LEVEL SOFT-SWITCHING POWER AMPLIFIERS

The flying capacitor multilevel soft-switching power amplifier (FCMLSSPA) is an architecture for driving MRI gradient coils, where high-precision current delivery is really important [36]. However, the inherent unbalance of flying capacitor voltages often degrades output current accuracy. To address this, this study proposes a novel voltage balancing strategy utilizing ladder filter inductor current and carrier phase-shift reconstruction. Authors establish a rigorous mathematical model of the FCMLSSPA topology, analyzing multilevel voltage and inductor current behavior across diverse operating conditions. A core focus is the comprehensive examination of the trapezoidal filter inductor current. By analyzing the transition mechanisms of the ten

FIGURE 12. Measured output magnitude (a), phase (b), power (c), dissipated power (d), and efficiency (e) of the RFPA module output versus RF_{REF} power [4].

distinct soft-switching states, the study dynamically allocates six key time domains. This allocation is based on the current circulation path and the objective of minimizing errors in the equivalent average current of the trapezoidal filter. Furthermore, the carrier phase-shift modulation is designed to satisfy initial voltage balance conditions, accounting for the flying capacitor’s initial state. When integrated with the dynamically reconstructed trapezoidal filtering current, this approach achieves stable capacitor voltage across multiple switching cycles throughout the entire operating range. The proposed theory was validated using a 700-W experimental prototype, demonstrating significant improvements in voltage stability and current precision [36].

The seven-level flying capacitor soft-switching power amplifier addressed in this study offers a high-density solution for MRI gradient driving by effectively distributing voltage stress across multiple semiconductor switches, thereby enabling stable high-voltage and high-current operation beyond the limits of individual devices [37]. To overcome the inherent voltage unbalance of flying capacitors, this research introduces an active balancing strategy centered on the dynamic reconstruction of the trapezoidal filter inductor current and carrier phase-shift modulation. You can view the topology in Fig. 13. By mathematically modeling the amplifier’s ten soft-switching transition states and dynamically allocating six key time domains, the proposed control logic minimizes equivalent average current errors while ensuring capacitor voltage stability across multiple switching cycles.

To validate the active balancing control algorithm, a simulation was performed using Simulink with a DC bus voltage of 250 V, a switching frequency range of 5 kHz to 10 kHz, and a load consisting of a 5Ω resistance and 20 mH inductance. The flying capacitor was modeled at 220 μF. Using a sinusoidal set point current with an 18 A amplitude at 50 Hz, the simulation verified that the output current precisely tracks the reference. As shown in the waveforms of Fig. 14, the seven-level output voltage effectively generates the required

FIGURE 13. Flying capacitor seven-level soft-switching power amplifier [36].

FIGURE 14. Output current i_{out} and output voltage u_{out} [36].

current, exhibiting the expected phase difference characteristic of the inductive load [38], [39].

This study introduces a robust active voltage balancing strategy for the Flying Capacitor Multilevel Soft-Switching Power Amplifier (FCMLSSPA) that optimizes MRI gradient performance by integrating carrier phase-shift reconstruction with a dynamically reconstructed trapezoidal filter current. The proposed control logic identifies critical operational modes that drive capacitor fluctuations and employs dynamic time allocation to minimize equivalent average current errors, achieving a precise charge-discharge equilibrium within a single switching cycle. Validated through both Simulink and a 700-W prototype, this hardware-free method ensures stable capacitor voltages across the entire operating range without compromising the high current fidelity required for gradient encoding. Furthermore, the iterative optimization framework is theoretically scalable to any multilevel flying capacitor topology, offering a versatile path for high-voltage, high-precision power conversion in advanced MRI systems.

G. HIGH POWER WIDEBAND CLASS-E POWER AMPLIFIER

Ortega-Gonzalez presents a high-power, high-efficiency Class-E RF power amplifier designed for the 85 to 120 MHz range, utilizing a novel load admittance synthesis concept and a power Silicon LDMOS transistor [40]. By leveraging a low-loss wideband admittance transformer as the primary component, the design achieves a peak output power of 145 W at 28 V with a 15.6 dB gain, specifically demonstrating an exceptional peak drain efficiency of 86% across a 35% fractional bandwidth. Unlike traditional designs that struggle with the low load impedances required by high-power transistors at fundamental and harmonic frequencies, this Class-E architecture effectively incorporates active-device parasitics, such as output capacitance and

non-zero switching times, into the matching network. This synthesis approach not only minimizes dissipative losses but also provides a significant performance leap over conventional Class-C or lower-power Class-E VHF amplifiers, offering critical advantages for MRI and aeronautical communications by reducing thermal management requirements and enabling more compact, reliable transmitter systems.

The output circuit of the Class-E amplifier which you can view in Fig. 15 is centered around a Freescale MRF6V4300N silicon LDMOS transistor. To ensure accurate simulation, the transistor is represented by a switching model that utilizes a nonlinear resistor (r_{ON}) for the “on” state and a series combination of nonlinear capacitance (C_{OUT}) and resistance (r_{OUT}) for the “off” state. A critical aspect of the design is the management of three distinct load planes: LP1, LP2, and LP3, where the package inductance (L_{PKG}) is identified as the most significant parasitic challenge to synthesizing the required Class-E admittance at the internal switch. By driving the transistor with a high-amplitude sinusoidal signal to enforce hard switching, the design successfully mitigates the inductive reactance of the package, allowing the subsequent wideband admittance transformer to provide the optimal load conditions necessary for high-efficiency VHF power amplification.

The harmonic termination network for this Class-E RFPA was synthesized from a six-element Chebyshev band-pass filter and refined through computer optimization to maintain the specific load phase angle required for nominal Class-E operation across a 75 to 135 MHz range [40]. By ensuring that the load admittance remained purely reactive at the second and third harmonics, the design effectively suppressed harmonic power dissipation. Simulations conducted via Agilent’s Advanced Design System (ADS) showed strong agreement with experimental results obtained using a high-precision wattmeter, confirming that the output power scales with the square of the drain bias. Results can be seen in Fig. 16. While measured efficiency marginally exceeded simulated values, the measured drain-to-source voltage waveforms at 100 MHz verified the high-efficiency switching behavior characteristic of the Class-E topology which can be seen in Fig. 17. This rigorous validation process highlights the amplifier’s ability to deliver high-power performance while operating close to theoretical zero-voltage switching conditions, which is crucial for reducing the thermal footprint in high-duty-cycle MRI applications.

This research concludes with the demonstration of a high-efficiency, wideband VHF power amplifier that represents a significant advancement over existing commercial and academic benchmarks for the 85–120 MHz range. By synthesizing the approximate load admittance necessary for nominal Class-E operation at both the fundamental and harmonic frequencies, the design minimizes dissipative losses while maximizing power transfer. The architecture’s performance is primarily attributed to a simplified, low-loss load network featuring a high-performance wideband transformer that optimizes the load impedance directly at the

FIGURE 15. Scheme of the amplifier output circuit [40].

FIGURE 16. Measured and simulated output power P_{out} and drain efficiency η_D [40].

FIGURE 17. Measured $V_{DS}(t)$ at 100 MHz and 12 V_{DC} [40].

transistor drain. This design methodology successfully overcomes traditional bandwidth-efficiency trade-offs, offering a robust and scalable solution for demanding applications such as high-field MRI and aeronautical communications where thermal management and compact integration are critical.

H. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF A LOW-COST, TABLETOP MRI SCANNER FOR EDUCATION AND RESEARCH PROTOTYPING

Cooley et al. explain the development and large-scale deployment of 20 low-cost, open-source tabletop MRI scanners designed to democratize MR physics education by providing an accessible, transparent alternative to prohibitively expensive commercial systems [41]. Unlike high-field clinical scanners or existing compact research systems, this platform prioritizes flexibility and educational transparency by offering fully open-source board files, pulse sequences, and reconstruction code accessible via customizable GUIs. The successful parallel operation of these 20 scanners for over 800 students highlights the design’s suitability for teaching fundamental signal processing and imaging principles while serving as a modular testbed for advanced MR research in resource-limited academic settings.

The tabletop MRI scanner incorporates a classic active PIN diode quarter-wave T/R switch integrated with the preamplifier (Fig. 18 (A)) on a single PCB to ensure efficient signal routing and hardware protection. During transmission, the console’s TX gating signal forward-biases the PIN diodes, establishing a low-impedance path to the coil while a lumped-element 50Ω π -network transforms a shunt-to-ground into a high-impedance barrier to isolate the preamplifier. Conversely, in receive mode, the diodes transition to a high-impedance state, connecting the coil to the preamp while decoupling the transmit chain. The system utilizes low-power amplifiers, such as the Mini-Circuits ZHL-3A ($\sim 1W$) or the Motorola MHW592 ($\sim 700mW$), the latter of which provides superior switching transients for the integrated power-blanking circuit. This blanking circuit (Fig. 18(B)), featuring a 7824-based regulator, was specifically implemented to mitigate DC artifacts caused by oscillator leakage during signal reception, though future iterations could leverage reverse DC biasing or push-pull blanking architectures to further enhance isolation and noise performance in high-density educational environments [42], [43].

The gradient power amplifier for this tabletop system was engineered for low cost and ease of fabrication, utilizing a pair of fault-protected OPA549 operational amplifiers in a push-pull (Class AB) configuration to deliver at least 5A of current over a 10kHz bandwidth. To ensure the high-precision current delivery required for spatial encoding, the design employs a feedback control loop centered on a 0.1Ω current sense resistor and a TI-INA105 difference amplifier, which provides a buffered feedback signal to a TI-OPA228 summing amplifier. This topology which you can examine in Fig. 19 maintains a constant current output proportional to the input control voltage, effectively compensating for disturbances such as inductive coupling from adjacent gradient coils. Frequency compensation components within the feedback loop stabilize the system against phase delays introduced by the $10\mu H$ load

FIGURE 18. (A) Combined T/R switch and pre-amplifier schematic. (B) Blanking circuit schematic [41].

FIGURE 19. Gradient power amplifier schematic [41].

impedance, enabling the GPA to achieve rapid settling times with 0 to 3A transitions in under 30μs [44].

The imaging performance of the tabletop MRI scanner was validated using 2D and 3D RARE sequences. Comparative testing against a 4.7T Bruker animal scanner revealed that while the tabletop system exhibited a lower SNR (15 vs. 23) and slight geometric distortion due to its 13X lower B₀ field and gradient calibration errors, it achieved a high spatial resolution. Results can be seen in Fig. 20. Notably, the system resolved 150μm capillary tube walls, demonstrating that this low-cost, open-source platform provides sufficient fidelity. The deployment of these low-cost tabletop MRI scanners and their associated MATLAB-based graphical user interfaces has successfully introduced over 800 students to core principles of MR physics, signal processing, and electrical engineering while doubling as a robust, open-source prototyping platform for advanced research. By providing full transparency in the design and implementation of hardware modules, the project encourages a collaborative ecosystem where the global MR community can contribute hardware upgrades and software enhancements. This accessible architecture not only facilitates the teaching of fundamental imaging concepts but also lowers the barrier to entry for researchers to develop and test novel pulse sequences or RF hardware in a modular, low-risk environment.

I. EVEN-ODD MODE EXCITATION FOR STABILITY INVESTIGATION OF CARTESIAN FEEDBACK AMPLIFIER USED IN PARALLEL TRANSMIT ARRAY

Shooshtary and Solbach address the critical challenge of ensuring unconditional stability in a 32-channel, 7T parallel transmit system where 1 kW Cartesian feedback power

FIGURE 20. (A and B) Phantom images acquired with a Bruker 4.7T animal scanner. (C-D) Images acquired with the tabletop scanner [41].

amplifiers are located in close proximity to the magnet [45]. Because high magnetic flux precludes the use of traditional circulators or isolators, the system relies on a Cartesian feedback loop to sample V_{out} and compensate for the mismatched load impedances (Z_{load}) caused by mutual coupling between adjacent coils. A simplified version of cartesian feedback loop can be seen in Fig. 21. Since Z_{load} varies as a function of self-impedance (Z₁₁), mutual impedance (Z₁₂), and specific excitation modes, the authors propose an efficient stability check method, utilizing pole-zero mapping and even-odd mode excitation analysis, as a simpler alternative to complex MIMO control theory. This approach allows researchers to identify the stability limits imposed by coil-to-coil interactions and ensures that the feedback loops remain robust across arbitrary excitation profiles, ultimately maintaining the RF homogeneity required for high-resolution 7T imaging.

The proposed stability analysis for the Cartesian feedback system leverages a symmetrical two-port circuit model to calculate the dynamic load impedance (Z_{load}) resulting from various coil excitation modes. By applying even-mode and odd-mode excitations, the network symmetry allows for the reduction of the system into identical sub-circuits governed by open-circuit and short-circuit conditions at the symmetry plane. The result can be extended for arbitrary excitation mode for coupled coils [45] and can be seen in (6):

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_{out1} &= CV_{out2} \\
 I_{out1} &= CI_{out2} \\
 Z_{load} &= \frac{V_{out1}}{I_{out1}} = Z_{11} + \frac{1}{C}Z_{12} \\
 Z_{load} &= \left(\frac{Z_{open} + Z_{short}}{2}\right) + \left(\frac{Z_{open} - Z_{short}}{2C}\right) \quad (6)
 \end{aligned}$$

This method enables a deterministic calculation of Z_{load} for any given excitation profile, which is subsequently integrated into a pole-zero mapping framework to evaluate closed-loop stability boundaries. This structured approach eliminates the need for selecting arbitrary load impedances and is validated

FIGURE 21. Simplified Cartesian feedback loop amplifier [45].

FIGURE 22. Simplified block diagram of Cartesian feedback Power amplifier with uncoupled coil load [45].

FIGURE 23. Scattering parameters for coupled coil [45].

FIGURE 24. Time domain simulation response of coupled Cartesian feedback system for $|C| = 1$ and $c = 0^\circ, 180^\circ$ and 270° [45].

through a high correlation between time-domain simulations and pole-mapping predictions, providing a robust pathway for assessing the stability of high-channel-count pTx arrays in 7T MRI environments.

The power amplifier is characterized as a linear voltage-controlled voltage source with a transfer function, $PA(s)$, whose frequency-dependent behavior is captured by an integrated band-pass filter. The system's Cartesian feedback architecture (Fig. 22) utilizes a voltage divider to sample the output voltage, which is subsequently down-converted and compared against the reference signal before being up-converted by a modulator to rectify errors. While the

feedback loop remains dormant under matched load conditions, any shift in equilibrium caused by antenna mismatch or mutual coupling from neighboring coils triggers the feedback mechanism to maintain signal fidelity. This modeling approach simplifies the complex high-power RF chain by assuming fixed impedance terminations for each functional block, allowing for the discrete derivation of transfer functions essential for stability analysis in high-channel-count pTx arrays. Using Agilent's Advanced Design System, the authors simulated a representative two-coil array to derive the scattering parameters (S_{11} and S_{12}), which provide the baseline for evaluating how load variations influence the cartesian feedback's closed-loop stability. Results can be seen in Fig. 23. By grounding the electrical model in these specific parasitic values, the study establishes a realistic framework for identifying the impedance boundaries at which the high-power feedback loops may transition from stable operation to oscillation in a high-density 7T MRI array. To validate the analytical predictions of the pole-mapping method, time-domain simulations were performed for various coupling coefficients ($|C| = 1$). The resulting waveforms (Fig. 24) exhibit smooth exponential transitions without evidence of sustained oscillations or divergence, confirming the accuracy of the frequency-domain stability boundaries.

This study demonstrates that the load impedance variations inherent to high-channel-count pTx arrays can be effectively analyzed for stability using a superposition of even-odd modes. While unconventional Cartesian feedback architectures introduce a power-dependent open-loop gain under mismatched conditions, the proposed framework allows for the identification of critical excitation vectors through linear mapping, providing a scalable methodology for ensuring unconditional stability across large-scale $N \times N$ coupling matrices. This approach represents a significant advancement for 7T MRI systems by offering a deterministic path to maintaining feedback loop integrity in the presence of complex coil-to-coil interactions.

J. HIGH-POWER RADIO FREQUENCY AMPLIFIER FOR 5-T MRI WHOLE-BODY SCANNER

Chen et al. present ultrahigh-field MRI technology by developing a reconfigurable RF power amplifier capable of a peak power output of 64kW, the highest reported value for 5T whole-body imaging [46]. Addressing the critical B_1^+ inhomogeneity and flip-angle limitations in deep body regions caused by short RF wavelengths, the authors proposed a novel impedance matching design that optimizes the power capability of individual transistors, significantly surpassing the conventional 1kW per-device threshold. The architecture features an innovative, modular transmit design that can be dynamically configured into eight, four, or two-channel modes, maintaining high gain linearity across all operating states.

In this work, the RFPA's power generation is modeled using Class AB LDMOS transistors, where the selection of

FIGURE 25. Equivalent circuit model of RF LDMOS and output impedance [46].

FIGURE 27. Matching circuit of MRFX1K80H. Circuit schematic [46].

FIGURE 26. Block diagram and photograph of multichannel RFPA for UHF MRI [46].

the device and the precision of the output matching circuit are paramount for maximizing power capability. By modeling the LDMOS (Fig. 25) as a voltage-controlled current source and transforming the standard series output impedance into a parallel configuration of resistance and reactance, the authors establish a direct analytical relationship between power output and load conditions [47], [48].

The design methodology for 64 kW RFPA centers on a novel output matching strategy that pushes a single LDMOS transistor to a 2.4 kW output, significantly exceeding its standard datasheet rating. To overcome the high measurement errors typical of low-impedance matching at high frequencies [49], the authors replaced direct instrumentation with 3-D electromagnetic simulations to precisely map the relationship between LDMOS package parasitics, bond-wire inductance, and circuit parameters. This hardware architecture which you can examine in Fig. 26 is uniquely modular, utilizing a specialized transmit selection and power combiner unit that allows the 64-kW total capacity to be reconfigured into eight, four, or two independent channels.

The final stage of the amplifier module utilizes NXP MRFX1K80H LDMOS transistors, which are configured in a push-pull architecture through the use of input and output baluns to effectively suppress harmonic distortion. The output matching circuit is constructed from a combination of capacitors, baluns, and planar transmission lines (TLs), with the specific choice of planar TLs over lumped inductors

FIGURE 28. Power capability (a) and efficiency test results (b) of MRFX1K80H corresponding to simulated R_L and X_L [46].

driven by the need for superior heat dissipation in high-power applications. You can see the matching circuit in Fig. 27.

Experimental results confirm that the proposed matching method enables each MRFX1K80H LDMOS transistor to achieve a peak power output of 2.4 kW by optimizing the load resistance to 3.1Ω and reactance to 3.5Ω. Operating in Class AB mode, the single-transistor power efficiency reached 62%, falling well within the theoretical range of 50–78.5% and ensuring that thermal dissipation remains manageable during high-power operation. While exceeding the rated power typically raises reliability concerns, the authors highlight that the pulsed nature of MRI duty cycles, dictated by overexcitation and Specific Absorption Rate (SAR) limits, results in a significantly lower average power dissipation compared to the continuous-mode testing used for standard ratings. You can examine the power capability and efficiency test results in Fig. 28.

FIGURE 29. Amplifier design with a single dual-tuned gate driver in preamplification stage and high and low frequency CMCD power stages connected to the nested coil configuration [50].

FIGURE 30. Simplified circuit diagram of optically generated tuning voltage control [50].

FIGURE 31. Photo of the adaptable dual-tuned on-coil amplifier with probes connected to the output of the preamplification stage [50].

The study concludes by demonstrating that the proposed 64 kW RFPA successfully addresses the critical power and hardware compatibility barriers inherent to ultrahigh-field whole-body imaging. By utilizing a novel impedance matching approach that pushes individual LDMOS transistors to a 2.4 kW peak, the system achieves the B_1^+ field strengths required for uniform contrast in deep-tissue regions at 5T. The modular architecture, featuring a built-in transmit selection and power combiner unit, allows the total power to be flexibly redistributed across eight, four, or two channels without the usual underutilization of installed capacity.

K. ADAPTABLE DUAL-TUNED OPTICALLY CONTROLLED ON-COIL RF POWER AMPLIFIER FOR MRI

Gudino introduces an adaptable, optically controlled RF power amplifier designed for direct on-coil integration in

7T multinuclear MRI applications [50]. To address the need for dual-tuned hardware capable of exciting both ^1H and various X-nuclei, she implemented an automated tuning mechanism centered on a voltage-modulated inductor within the gate driver of the FET switches. This configuration allows the amplifier to dynamically shift its operating frequency from the control console, facilitating the co-registration of high-resolution anatomical images with metabolically significant X-nuclei data. By replacing bulky, fixed-frequency remote amplifiers with these versatile on-coil units, the system achieves a more efficient and simplified hardware architecture, significantly reducing transmission losses and enhancing the signal-to-noise ratio for low-gamma nuclei in ultra-high field environments.

The proposed optically controlled on-coil RFPA represents a paradigm shift from traditional amplification architectures [51] by integrating a current-mode class-D switch-mode topology directly onto the 7T transmit coil. This configuration bypasses the inherent limitations of conventional multinuclear chains by eliminating 50 Ω coaxial interconnects. The design achieves its frequency agility through a unique dual-resonant LC network architecture, where the X-nuclei frequency is dynamically adjusted using an effective voltage-modulated inductor realized via a Gallium Nitride FET.

The adaptable dual-tuned amplifier architecture is designed to support both single multi-tuned coils and nested coil configurations, with the latter being the primary focus due to its ability to eliminate efficiency trade-offs. The system is entirely optically controlled via a 1 GBd optical transceiver, which feeds a wideband voltage amplifier and a Class-D push-pull preamplification stage. In the nested configuration, this preamplifier drives two distinct Current-Mode Class-D output stages: a fixed stage and a tunable stage. The diagram is shown in Fig. 29. A key innovation in this design is the optical generation of the tuning voltage which can be seen in Fig. 30. By modulating the duty cycle of a 10MHz optical pulse, the system rectifies the signal on-board to create a stable DC control voltage for the variable inductor. This allows for rapid, software-defined frequency shifts between MRI repetitions without physical intervention.

Bench measurements (Fig. 31) confirm the effectiveness of the tunable inductor and the robustness of the push-pull gate driver. The preamplifier successfully generated out-of-phase voltage signals exceeding 5V, ensuring high-efficiency switching of the power-stage FETs. Initial manual characterization, varying the tuning voltage from 0 to 40V, demonstrated a tunable bandwidth of 75 to 104 MHz, aligning closely with theoretical simulations.

The study concludes by demonstrating that adaptable, dual-tuned on-coil RF power amplification can significantly simplify 7T multinuclear MRI hardware by eliminating conventional components like cable traps, matching networks, and decoupling circuitry. The system's core innovation is a novel tunable device consisting of a fixed inductor in series with the voltage-modulated output capacitance of ultra-small

FIGURE 32. Block diagram of simulation setup for one meander coil with Cartesian feedback loop [54].

FIGURE 33. Power amplifier transfer characteristics with and without feedback loop (a) magnitude, (b) phase, (c) gain [54].

package GaN FETs. By exploiting the well-defined C_{OSS} characteristics of these FETs, the researchers achieved a programmable bandwidth of 74 to 90 MHz, enabling the excitation of metabolically relevant nuclei such as ^{13}C , ^{23}Na , and ^{129}Xe . While the current implementation was limited by a 22 V maximum optical tuning voltage, the integration of on-board current sensing offers a path toward fully automated self-tuning and optimization. This versatile technology paves the way for a single, layer-reduced RF hardware interface that could fundamentally increase the accessibility and efficiency of multinuclear clinical workflows [52], [53].

L. POWER AMPLIFIER FOR MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING USING UNCONVENTIONAL CARTESIAN FEEDBACK LOOP

Abuelhaija et al. work on a power amplifier featuring an unconventional cartesian feedback loop designed to

maintain a constant current in the RF coil despite the significant impedance mismatches caused by patient loading in 7T MRI systems [54]. Unlike traditional systems that rely on time-consuming manual or complex mechanical tuning, this approach integrates built-in coil current sensing directly into a near-magnet pulse power amplifier. By sampling the actual coil current rather than the forward voltage, the unconventional feedback loop can dynamically compensate for detuning and mismatch. The research provides a comprehensive framework validated by measurements of a prototype amplifier. This architecture offers a robust alternative to automatic impedance matching systems, potentially streamlining clinical workflows by ensuring stable transmit performance without the need for discrete remotely-switched capacitor arrays or varactor-based tuning.

By maintaining V_{out} constant at the amplifier output through an unconventional Cartesian feedback loop, the system ensures a stable coil current despite variations in patient loading or mutual coupling.

The feedback loop integrates an IQ-modulator, IQ-demodulator, active 1st-order low-pass filters, and a phase shifter to regulate the drive signal (Fig. 32). To achieve a balance between efficiency and linearity, the system utilizes a Class AB power amplifier that is linearized via an unconventional Cartesian feedback loop. When operating near the compression point to maximize power efficiency, amplifiers typically exhibit significant AM-AM and AM-PM distortions, where the output deviates from a linear response. The Cartesian feedback mechanism effectively suppresses this “bending” by continuously aligning the output magnitude and phase with the reference input. Simulation results in ADS which can be seen in Fig. 33, demonstrate that the loop successfully maintains a constant gain and linear transfer characteristic right up to the point of full saturation, ensuring that the high-power pulses required for MRI remain undistorted even as the amplifier transitions into its non-linear operating region. The prototype of the control and pre-amplification stage was implemented using a series of specialized RF components to manage the unconventional Cartesian feedback loop (Fig. 34). To ensure stable feedback, an AD8309 logarithmic amplifier provides a constant-level Local Oscillator signal to the HMC597 I/Q demodulator, regardless of variations in input power. This sophisticated control chain, toggled via an I2C-controlled register or manual switch, allows for precise phase and amplitude regulation of the 1 kW LDMOS final stage, effectively forcing a constant current into the MRI coil under varying load conditions [55].

The HMC597 downconverter acts as a high-precision comparator, utilizing its on-chip RF balun to calculate the vector difference between the RF reference input and a sampled version of the controlled output. Under perfectly matched conditions, the signals are aligned in amplitude and phase, generating no quadrature error. However, when mismatch or mutual coupling occurs, the resulting quadrature signals are processed through AD8132 active low-pass filters (16dB gain, 160 kHz bandwidth) to drive the vector modulator

FIGURE 37. (a) A single bootstrapped half-bridge driver circuit. (b) Simulated coil current (top) and Q-switch current (bottom) under ring-down conditions for $V_{D+} = 125\text{ V}$ [56].

FIGURE 38. Photograph of the PA [56].

FIGURE 39. (a) Measured voltage at node V_{N1} and current passes I_{LF1} . (b) Measured voltage of the coil at the end of the pulse when the Q-switch is disabled (top) and enabled (bottom) [56].

supply voltage of $V_{D+} = 125\text{ V}$ and a duty cycle of 35%, the amplifier achieves a steady-state output within just two RF cycles, delivering approximately 350 W of power to the coil at 2 MHz. Furthermore, the active Q-switch ensures a rapid coil ring-down within 4 μs , and the multi-pulse sequence capability supports a repetition period of up to 390 μs , making this compact architecture ideal for high-SNR measurements in field-deployable low-field spectrometers.

N. RADIOFREQUENCY POWER AMPLIFIERS FOR NMR AND MRI

Myer provides a foundational and comprehensive overview of RF power amplifier technology, specifically tailored for technologists and engineers working with NMR spectrometers and MRI scanners [59]. It bridges the gap between raw RF performance and clinical image quality by examining how amplifier specifications directly influence the integrity of RF pulse sequences. The study covers the entire lifecycle of an RFPA concluding with a roadmap for future architectural trends in the field.

The standard architectural framework of an NMR/MRI RF power amplifier consists of a cascaded chain where divider and combiner networks are utilized to algebraically sum

outputs to achieve peak kilowatt levels. High level block diagram can be seen in Fig. 40. This system is governed by a microcontroller that monitors vital safety parameters such as duty factor, temperature, and VSWR via a directional coupler, triggering fault modes to prevent hardware damage from reflected power. At the circuit level, each stage relies on precise impedance matching networks to bridge the gap between the 50 Ω system standard and the low impedance of the RF transistors, alongside coupling and decoupling components that isolate DC and RF energy paths. Ultimately, while the RFPA aims to produce an exact, high-amplitude replica of the input signal, real-world components inevitably introduce distortions and pulse anomalies that must be characterized to ensure high-fidelity MRI performance.

Characterizing an RFPA requires analyzing performance across the time, frequency, and power domains to understand how variations in stimuli affect the response of the amplifier. In the time domain, rapid pulsing of transistors creates non-ideal transients such as bias enable/disable spikes and low-frequency distortions like pre shoot or post pulse back-swing caused by energy “fly wheeling” between internal decoupling inductors and coupling capacitors. While these transient signals can appear at the output, they are often negligible in MRI applications.

The frequency domain specifications of an RFPA define its performance consistency across different nuclear frequencies, ensuring reliable operation for both single-nucleus and multinuclear studies. Bandwidth establishes the range over which the amplifier maintains its rated power and linearity, while Power Gain is typically designed to raise a standard 1mW input to the required kilowatt level. The ideal linear and nonlinear amplifier transfer function is in Fig. 41. To ensure precision, Gain Flatness is specified both for broadband multinuclear coverage and more strictly for nucleus-centered windows. Furthermore, while the quasilinear transfer characteristics of power transistors inevitably introduce Harmonic Content at integral multiples of the input frequency, these distortions are usually negligible in MRI because the high-quality factor of the transmit coil effectively filters out harmonic energy.

The blanked output noise specification is critical for maintaining a high signal-to-noise ratio in MRI, as the extremely faint NMR signals can easily be overwhelmed by the inherent noise of a high-gain RFPA. To minimize this interference during the “listening” phase without the latency of a full system shutdown, amplifiers utilize a blanking technique that selectively cuts the bias to the final output transistor stages, allowing them to switch states in under a microsecond.

The power domain characterization of an RFPA involves sweeping input power across a dynamic range to monitor how the output power and phase respond to varying signal intensities. Maximum power requirements vary by clinical application, with 3T whole-body systems demanding up to 35 kW, while modern multichannel 7T arrays typically utilize 1 kW per channel. Gain nonlinearity can significantly distort the amplitude ratios required for precise pulse sequences,

FIGURE 40. RFPA architecture [59].

FIGURE 41. RFPA transfer functions [59].

FIGURE 42. RFPA test configuration [59].

making it essential to define a dynamic range within which the amplifier must maintain acceptable linearity to ensure high-fidelity imaging.

Testing and evaluating an RFPA's performance can be achieved effectively using standard equipment typically found in NMR/MRI facilities to verify compliance with core specifications. The test configuration can be seen in Fig. 42.

The required setup centers on a high-fidelity RF signal source and a high-speed RF switch to generate near-ideal test pulses, synchronized via a dual-channel pulse generator. A four-channel digital storage oscilloscope with a bandwidth at least three times the operating frequency is essential for monitoring the signals sampled through a dual directional coupler. To protect sensitive instrumentation while measuring kilowatt-level outputs, a series of high-power attenuators must be utilized, ensuring all cables and connectors are rated for the peak and average power levels of the amplifier under test.

The transition from traditional vacuum tube amplifiers to solid-state architectures represents a major shift in modern MRI, particularly as field strengths move toward 3T and beyond where B_1^+ field inhomogeneity becomes a critical hurdle. This architecture introduces unique challenges, such as mutual coupling between transmit elements, which can result in “virtual VSWR” faults where reflected power originates from neighboring coils rather than load mismatches.

O. DESIGN AND REALIZATION OF TIME-DOMAIN TRANSFER DPD METHOD FOR MRI RF POWER AMPLIFIERS

Li et al. introduce a novel Digital Pre-Distortion (DPD) method specifically tailored for MRI RFPAs, utilizing a Time-Domain Transform Model (TDTM) based on memory polynomials. The architecture addresses the persistent challenge of maintaining linearity over the extreme dynamic ranges (40–60 dB) and high-power levels required for 3.0-T MRI [60]. Unlike conventional DPD used in telecommunications, which often lacks time-domain memory considerations, this TDTM approach specifically compensates for AM/AM and AM/PM distortions that worsen near saturation. The system employs a dual-amplifier architecture, placing pre-distorters before both a 1-kW main amplifier and a 100-W auxiliary amplifier at 128 MHz. A directional coupler and ADC facilitate real-time feedback, allowing the DPD coefficients to update dynamically as linearity shifts during operation.

You can examine the proposed two-stage DPD architecture in Fig. 43 that optimizes MRI RFPA performance by utilizing a primary main power amplifier and a secondary auxiliary amplifier to iteratively eliminate residual nonlinearities. In this process, the input signal is split into identical paths, where pre-distorter 1 first linearizes the PAm output using an inverse model updated via real-time I/Q feedback. If $Y_1(n)$ still exhibits distortion, pre-distorter 2 generates a compensation signal through PAa, based on the remaining nonlinear inversion of the main stage. Finally, signal output is obtained from the combination of predistorter 2 and PAa, Y_{out} expressed as (7) [60]:

$$Y_{out}(n) = Y_1(n) + Y_2(n) \tag{7}$$

The nonlinearity of a 1-kW 3.0-T RFPA module is characterized in Fig. 44, which reveals significant raw gain variations of 5.2 dB and phase shifts of 25°. To counteract this, the

FIGURE 43. Architecture of the DPD for the MRI RFPA [60].

FIGURE 44. Nonlinearity model of the 1-kW RFPA power module: (a) AM/AM model; (a') AM/AM inverse model; (b) AM/PM model; and (b') AM/PM inverse model [60].

FIGURE 45. 3.0-T MRI RFPA of DPD imaging experimental results: (a) GRE sequence and (b) FSE sequence [60].

dual-stage DPD system utilizes an FPGA-based hardware setup where ADC1 digitizes the input signal to establish an initial inverse model, while a feedback ADC captures the output from a directional coupler to dynamically update coefficients. The first pre-distorter compensates for the bulk of the distortion, while a secondary pre-distorter and 100-W auxiliary amplifier targets the residual nonlinearities, effectively canceling the remaining error through in-phase combination. This comprehensive correction process, executed in real-time within the digital domain, ensures the final high-power output remains linear and stable, fulfilling the stringent fidelity requirements for high-resolution 3.0-T MRI.

The validation of the 1-kW 3.0-T MRI RFPA was completed through integration into a clinical Super Scan MRI system (Fig. 45), where it successfully produced high-quality images that met all SNR and efficiency requirements.

While the current 1-kW prototype is ideal for multichannel or smaller coil applications, the study highlights that the TDTM-DPD method is particularly essential for scaling toward the 20-kW power levels required for whole-body imaging.

The study concludes that the specialized TDTM-based DPD method is a highly effective solution for linearizing high-power MRI RFPAs, achieving significant reductions in signal distortion. By utilizing a memory-polynomial model that accounts for both time- and frequency-domain excitation, the architecture successfully reduced gain nonlinearity from 7.2 dB to 0.15 dB. The researchers emphasize that this method is easily scalable to higher power levels required for whole-body high-field scanners, where large-dimensional excitations demand extreme pulse fidelity. The final integration into a 3.0-T system confirmed that this digital feedforward and feedback approach provides the necessary stability and precision to produce high-quality clinical images while maintaining high efficiency.

P. ANALYSIS ON A PWM POWER CONVERSION AMPLIFIER WITH IGBT MACRO MODEL TO GENERATE GRADIENT MAGNETIC FIELDS IN MRI SYSTEMS

Watanabe et al. shift the focus from Radio Frequency Power Amplifiers to Gradient Power Amplifiers, proposing a high-power density PWM architecture designed for rapid gradient field generation [61]. The system utilizes a two-paralleled configuration of four-quadrant DC chopper circuits, incorporating a total of 8 IGBTs to handle the high current requirements of MRI gradient coils. To achieve the precise spatial resolution and fast rise/fall times necessitated by moving-organ diagnostics, the authors implement a sophisticated digital control scheme. This scheme utilizes optimal type-1 servo control combined with preview digital control to minimize current ripple and enhance robustness. By ensuring high-fidelity current tracking in the gradient coils, the proposed technique aims to significantly expand diagnostic capabilities and improve overall MRI image quality. Their PWM conversion amplifier can be seen in Fig. 46.

To overcome the limitations of ideal switching simulations, they propose an IGBT macro-model (Fig. 47) that utilizes variable resistance branches to accurately capture real-world parasitic behaviors such as internal resistance, saturation voltage, and the characteristic tail current. By simulating these non-ideal effects, the model allows for a precise estimation of total power losses and heat energy dissipation, which is essential for designing effective cooling systems and heat sinks in high-power gradient amplifiers. Furthermore, the ability to replicate the tail current enables engineers to establish the optimum dead-time and switching frequency limits required to prevent current overflow and ensure robust high-speed performance. This modeling approach is vital for the development of high-density power conversion circuits that maintain current tracking accuracy in MRI gradient coils.

The simulation results demonstrate that while the IGBTs used in the system are limited to a maximum stable switching

FIGURE 46. PWM power conversion amplifier with two paralleled four quadrant DC chopper in MRI systems [61].

FIGURE 47. The IGBT macro-model with the reversible current flowing in the paralleled diode [61].

FIGURE 48. Simulation results of current tracking control in MRI systems [61].

frequency of 20 kHz, they are capable of handling substantial power levels exceeding 1000 V/100 A. The simulation results (Fig. 48) for the 200-Hz ramped-square wave current demonstrate that the dual-paralleled IGBT architecture can drive a peak-to-peak current of 300 A into a 200 μ H gradient coil with remarkable precision.

This study demonstrates that a PWM power conversion amplifier utilizing two paralleled four-quadrant DC choppers can effectively overcome the low-frequency switching limitations of IGBTs to provide high-power output for MRI gradient coils. By implementing a specialized IGBT macro-model that accounts for real-world switching losses and tail currents, the researchers produced more reliable simulation data than traditional ideal models, allowing for the precise design of necessary heat sinks. Ultimately, this robust and accessible design is suitable for high-power industrial applications involving highly inductive coils and has been validated through computer-aided analysis as a viable path for high-fidelity MRI gradient field generation.

Q. HIGH-RESOLUTION CONTROL METHOD FOR ULTRA-HIGH-POWER AMPLIFIER IN MRI

Yu et al. work on ultra-high-power gradient amplifiers for MRI, targeting the MVA power level while maintaining PPM resolution [62]. While traditional cascaded multilevel H-bridge topologies often rely on PID feedback and feed-forward loops, they suffer from complex, time-consuming tuning and a lack of precise pole placement. To solve this, the authors develop an order-reduced state space controller (Fig. 49) that simplifies the mathematical complexity of a system with numerous components without sacrificing the high-fidelity current tracking required for image reconstruction.

By representing the inverter’s output as a constant voltage over each PWM interval, the controller synchronizes its state-vector calculations directly with the power stage’s switching frequency. This modeling approach is fundamental to achieving PPM-level resolution, as it ensures that the high-current commands are mapped accurately to the discrete voltage steps required to drive the highly inductive gradient coils with minimal quantization error. Simplified structure can be seen in Fig. 50. To address the high costs and synchronization delays inherent in measuring every state variable of a complex MVA-level amplifier, they develop an order-reduced state space controller that prioritizes the primary control objective while strategically ignoring the state variables of the output filter (Fig. 51). By establishing state equations for this simplified model and applying discrete-time pole placement the architecture achieves a significant reduction in system complexity without compromising high-resolution performance [63].

The experimental validation of the 1400 V / 900 A ultra-high-power amplifier demonstrator utilized a high-performance hardware stack featuring SiC power modules for the power stages and an FPGA-based controller for rapid processing. To ensure precision, a high-resolution flux-gate current sensor was employed alongside a standard low-pass output filter. The system’s robustness was confirmed by generating a 900 A trapezoidal current pulse, which successfully achieved a peak amplitude of 900 A with an exceptionally fast rising edge of only 0.21 ms. This result proves that the order-reduced state space control method enables these massive MVA-level amplifiers to meet the stringent requirements for high current amplitude and short settling times necessary for high-fidelity MRI gradient field generation.

The final experimental evaluation of the 1400 V / 900 A amplifier confirms its ability to maintain extreme linearity (Fig. 52), which is critical for preventing spatial distortions in MRI reconstruction. The system achieved a non-linearity of less than 0.75 %, comfortably surpassing the industry’s strict requirement of 1 %. While minor deviations were observed at the positive and negative peak currents, the researchers attributed this to the performance ceiling of the flux-gate current sensor rather than the amplifier itself. These results validate that the order-reduced state space controller and SiC

FIGURE 49. Block diagram of classical control method. I_{ref} indicates the input reference signal [62].

FIGURE 50. Simplified structure diagram of power amplifier [62].

FIGURE 51. Block diagram of order-reduced state space controller [62].

FIGURE 52. Non-linearity of the power amplifier [62].

power modules can successfully deliver MVA-level power with the PPM-level precision needed for high-fidelity gradient magnetic fields.

The conclusion solidifies the effectiveness of the order-reduced state space control method in managing the complexities of an MVA-level power system. Benchmarks prove that the approach provides the high-fidelity current tracking necessary for ultra-high-resolution MRI, effectively bridging the gap between massive power delivery and microscopic signal precision. The researchers emphasize that this “simpler yet highly accurate” control logic is not limited to

MRI but is a scalable solution for any high-resolution power converter application.

R. POWER DIVIDERS/COMBINERS FOR 1.5T MRI SOLID STATE POWER AMPLIFIER

Boricha et al. evaluate various power combining and dividing technologies for 1.5-T Solid-State Power Amplifiers, focusing on the design and fabrication of a high-power 4:1 Wilkinson combiner that utilizes a novel coaxial cable assembly to achieve a peak output power of 5 kW [64]. By comparing traditional microstrip Wilkinson dividers with the Gysel divider, which features grounded isolation resistors for improved heat dissipation, and lumped-element equivalents necessary for lower VHF/UHF bands, the paper highlights the critical trade-offs between simplicity, power density, and physical size.

The conventional Wilkinson Combiner represents a fundamental advancement over T-junction and corporate dividers by providing both simultaneous port matching and high port-to-port isolation through the strategic placement of isolation resistors. As a reciprocal and symmetric device, its design relies on quarter-wave ($\lambda/4$) transmission lines with a characteristic impedance which can be seen in (8):

$$Z_1 = Z_0 \sqrt{N} \tag{8}$$

where N is the number of input ports [64].

The Gysel Combiner improves upon the Wilkinson architecture by providing significantly higher power handling and robust thermal management, making it a preferred choice for high-intensity MRI RF systems. Unlike the Wilkinson design where isolation resistors are “floating,” the Gysel topology utilizes a configuration where the isolation resistors are grounded. This grounding allows excess power from port failures or mismatches to be safely dissipated to the chassis, preventing catastrophic mutual coupling and reflections that could occur at power levels in the tens of kilowatts. While this added complexity results in a bulkier footprint compared to Wilkinson combiners, the enhanced reliability and ability to dump reflected power to ground make it essential for industrial-scale SSPAs. However, when transitioning from microstrip to coaxial cable implementations, designers must balance these “degrees of freedom” with the practical constraints of using commercially available cable impedances. A basic 2-way Gysel divider is shown in Fig. 53. The limitations of traditional $\lambda/4$ lines at VHF frequencies drive the adoption of loading techniques and lumped-element architectures for 1.5-T MRI combiners. While capacitive loading can electrically shorten the line to lengths like $\lambda/16$, it causes the required microstrip width to shrink to tens of micrometers, making it impossible to fabricate and unable to handle the high current densities of an SSPA. Inductive loading offers a similar path to compactness but shares these fabrication hurdles. Consequently, for power levels reaching hundreds of watts, the microstrip approach is abandoned in favor of lumped-element Wilkinson and Gysel combiners,

FIGURE 53. Gysel power divider [64].

TABLE 4. Results of various techniques [64].

Parameter / Topology	Capacitive Loading	Inductive Loading	Lumped Wilkinson	Gysel (Co-axial Cable)	Wilkinson (Co-axial Cable)
Return Loss (dB)	41.90	53.15	206.04	49.67	61.64
Insertion Loss (dB)	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.16	0.11
Isolation Loss (dB)	41.47	51.32	177.37	58.51	53.02
Bandwidth (MHz)	44.71	42.37	16.9	15.92	29.41

which replace transmission lines entirely with lossless LC networks [65].

The simulation results obtained via Keysight ADS using an ARLON 350 substrate confirm that while various topologies can meet the standard requirements of Return loss < -15dB, Insertion loss < 0.2 dB, and Isolation loss < -15 dB, significant trade-offs exist as power requirements escalate toward 20 kW. Although lumped-element designs offer the necessary compactness for 1.5T applications, they are physically insufficient for the 5 to 20 kW range, where the conventional Wilkinson topology using a coaxial design emerges as the most reliable compromise between simplicity and high-power handling. Table 4 shows the results obtained after simulations. The study also highlights that Gysel combiners provide superior power management but suffer from increased complexity and reduced bandwidth when scaled for multiple inputs, whereas capacitive/inductive loading provides harmonic suppression at the cost of limited power resilience. Ultimately, the paper concludes that for modern 1.5 T systems reaching 20 kW levels, there is an urgent need to explore compact, high-power architectures that move beyond traditional quarter-wave transmission lines to maintain high-fidelity pulse delivery.

S. EFFECT OF DIFFERENT OVERSAMPLING RATIOS FOR SWITCH MODE AMPLIFIERS IN LOW-FIELD MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING

The study by Ehses et al. compares the performance of a switch-mode power amplifier against a traditional Class A linear amplifier within a low-field MRI scanner, specifically examining how different oversampling ratios affect image quality [66]. While Class A amplifiers are prized for their low noise and minimal harmonic distortion, their low efficiency generates significant waste heat, which is a major

drawback for modern portable or high-channel-count systems. The researchers found that by increasing the oversampling ratio the average peak maximum of the acquired MRI spectra increased, improving the fidelity of both rectangular and sinc-shaped RF pulses. Ultimately, the study highlights that while SMPAs require filtering to manage harmonic distortion and more complex hardware for high-frequency switching, their superior power density and efficiency make them ideal candidates for the development of mobile, ambulance-ready MRI systems where weight and cooling capacity are strictly limited.

This study evaluates a self-developed single-ended Class D switch-mode amplifier against a traditional Class A linear amplifier using the OCRA Tabletop MRI system [67], which operates at a low-field strength of 0.26 T. To drive the switch-mode stage, analog RF pulses with rectangular and sinc envelopes are converted into digital bit-streams using a delta-sigma modulator synthesized in Matlab, which allows for adjustable oversampling ratios of 20, 10, and 5. These bit-streams are loaded onto an external FPGA and triggered by the system’s internal RedPitaya controller via a TX gate signal, effectively bypassing the standard linear amplifier to allow for a direct performance comparison during free induction decay and gradient echo sequences. This flexible hardware-software stack, managed by a Raspberry Pi host, provides a robust platform for analyzing how oversampling and noise-shaping affect excitation fidelity in portable, low-cost MRI environments. Test setup for the switch mode amplifier is shown in Fig. 54.

The experimental results for rectangular pulse excitation demonstrate that the single-ended Class D switch-mode amplifier can effectively replicate the spin spectrum of a traditional linear amplifier at 11.4 MHz. Notably, at an OSR of 20, the SMPA’s peak height and noise floor align almost perfectly with those of the linear amplifier, yielding a comparable Signal-to-Noise Ratio. Interestingly, while decreasing the OSR results in a lower peak height, it also significantly reduces the noise level; consequently, the SNR at an OSR of 10 actually exceeds that of the linear amplifier. Similar trends were observed in gradient echo (GRE) projections in both x and z directions, where the SMPA maintained the general spectrum profile across all OSRs. Despite a slight frequency offset in the SMPA spectra, the data confirms that high-fidelity excitation is achievable, with higher oversampling ratios providing superior signal intensity for low-field imaging. FID spectrum and GRE projection spectrum can be seen in Fig. 55.

The experimental findings confirm that switch-mode amplifiers are capable of driving both rectangular and slice-selective sinc excitation pulses for MRI, though performance is heavily dependent on the oversampling ratio. A critical observation is that lower OSRs lead to reduced excitation amplitudes, resulting in a flip angle of less than the desired 90°; to maintain image contrast at low OSRs, the amplifier’s supply power must be proportionally increased to compensate. While lower OSRs initially appeared to reduce

FIGURE 54. Schematic measurement setup for measurements with the switch mode amplifier [66].

FIGURE 55. FID spectrum (left) and GRE projection spectrum (right) [66].

FIGURE 56. Input vs Output Power plot of 15kW amplifier [68].

noise, the researchers attribute this to potential measurement artifacts from the unshielded test environment rather than the amplifier architecture itself.

T. INDIGENOUS DEVELOPMENT OF 15KW RF POWER AMPLIFIER FOR 1.5T MRI SCANNER

This paper details the development of a 15-kW solid-state RF pulse amplifier designed specifically for the MRI system operating at 63.87 MHz by Bhuiya et al. [68]. The architecture utilizes high-performance LDMOS transistors, which replaced older BJT technology in the 1990s due to their superior gain and power density. To balance the strict requirements for signal fidelity and efficiency, the amplifier operates in Class AB, acting as a controlled current source to provide the linear amplification necessary for complex Pulse Sequence Diagrams without the heavy distortion of non-linear classes. This integration marks a step in localized medical diagnostic

TABLE 5. Final results of 1 kW system [69].

Sr. No.	Parameter	Value
1	Output power (Sat)	61.2 dBm
2	1dB (output)	60 dBm
3	Gain	21 dB
4	Droop	2.6 %
5	Rise time	79.92 ns
6	Fall time	42.12 ns
7	Delay	28.12 ns
8	Harmonics	Even: -55 dBc Odd: -30 dBc
9	Return loss	< -11.65 dB
10	Bandwidth	+/- 600 kHz
11	PAE	53.26 %
12	Gain flatness	+/- 0.25 dB

technology, suggesting high-contrast imaging of brain and soft tissues without the need for imported infrastructure.

The development scheme centers on a modular 15 kW RF power amplifier architecture operating at 63.87 MHz to support both full-body and head scans. The system is built around a foundational 1.25 kW amplifier module utilizing the MRF1K50H LDMOS transistor in a Class AB push-pull configuration. By successfully integrating 16 of these high-efficiency modules, the design achieves the high peak power required for 1.5-T imaging while maintaining the linearity necessary for precise proton excitation. This modular approach not only ensures scalability but also provides the redundancy and thermal stability essential for clinical diagnostic equipment.

The final 15-kW output system is achieved by combining four 3.5–4 kW stages through a ferrite-based broadband 4:1 combiner. The test results shown in Fig. 56. To ensure system safety and real-time performance tracking, a dual directional coupler extracts forward and reflected signals, enabling precise monitoring of VSWR and power levels. The architecture is fully supervised by a National Instruments controller and a LabVIEW-based GUI, which monitors 16 current and 16 temperature sensors to manage safety interlocks. The gain stages are built on a robust LDMOS pipeline: a MRFE6VS25N pre-driver (25 W, 14 dB gain) feeds a driver stage of the same device (25 W, 23 dB gain), which then drives the primary MRF1K50H LDMOS modules (1.25 kW each, 21 dB gain). This integrated 15-kW assembly has been successfully validated through a body birdcage coil, delivering high-fidelity clinical images while maintaining full operational stability under pulsed conditions at 63.87 MHz.

U. RF EXCITER CONTROL SYSTEM FOR HEAD IMAGING IN 1.5T MRI

Nerurkar et al. present the development of a 1-kW RF power amplifier operating at 63.87 MHz for 1.5-T MRI systems, with a specialized focus on the feedback control and monitoring infrastructure. To achieve this, they implemented a robust control system and a LabVIEW-based GUI. This setup provides real-time monitoring of critical metrics enabling

TABLE 6. Specifications of selected commercial amplifiers used in MRI.

RF amplifier	Peak Power (kW)	Number of Channels	Operating Frequency (MHz)	Max Duty Cycle (%)	Blanking Noise Level (dBm/Hz)	Pulse to rising / falling edge (μ s)	RF rise / fall transition time (μ s)	Minimum Pulse Length (μ s)	Harmonic Strength (dBc)
[71]	3	1	5-30	10	<-160 ^a -171.1 ^b	20 ^c	N/A	100	< -25
[72]	0.5	1	0.1-30	20	N/A-171.9 ^b	1 ^d	0.2 ^d	<10	\leq -12
[73]	0.5	1	0.1-10	10	20 dB ^a	1 ^d	1 ^d	N/A	< -12
[74]	18	1	63.87	50	< -150 ^a	50 ^d	N/A	100	< -40
[75]	0.1	1	100-600	100	< 10 dB	0.3/0.15 ^d	0.2/0.1 ^c	N/A	< -10
[76]	0.3	1	6-220	10	25 dB ^a	2 ^d	0.5 ^d	N/A	N/A
[77]	6	1	5-30	10	< -160 ^a	20 ^c	N/A	N/A	< -25

TABLE 7. Specifications of inspected amplifiers used in MRI.

RF amplifier	Field Strength	Topology	Output Frequency	Peak Output Power	Number of Channels	Duty Cycle (%)
[4]	3 T	LDMOS (Class AB)	1.25 MHz	130 W	Multi	10
[10]	5 T	LDMOS	210.78 MHz	8 kW	Multi	N/A
[16]	5 T	GaN HEMT	210.78 MHz	2 kW	N/A	20
[28]	0.22 T	Class AB	9.27 MHz	1 kW	Dual	50
[45]	7 T	Cartesian Feedback	N/A	1 kW	Multi	N/A
[46]	5 T	LDMOS (Class AB)	210.8 MHz	64 kW	8-4-2	N/A
[56]	N/A	GaNFET H-Bridge	2 MHz	350 W	N/A	48
[60]	3 T	Digital Pre-Distortion	128 MHz	1 kW	N/A	N/A
[64]	1.5 T	Wilkinson Combiner	63.87 MHz	5 kW	N/A	N/A
[68]	1.5 T	LDMOS (Class AB)	63.87 MHz	15 kW	N/A	10

automated safety interlocks. By integrating these rugged NI-based acquisition modules, the design ensures that the high-power LDMOS stages maintain the linearity and stability required for superior soft-tissue contrast without risking catastrophic component failure [69].

The component of this 1-kW RFPA design is the selection of Silicon LDMOS technology, chosen for its high-power gain, thermal stability, and superior linearity compared to legacy bipolar technologies. The system architecture follows a two-stage approach where a Driver Amplifier provides the initial gain necessary to push the Main Amplifier to its kilowatt-level output. This configuration ensures that the 63.87 MHz pulse maintains the strict spectral purity required for 1.5-T imaging while maximizing DC-to-RF efficiency [70].

This 1-kW RF power amplifier design for 1.5-T MRI utilizes a strategic hybrid topology, pairing a Class A driver for maximum linearity at lower power with a Class AB main amplifier to optimize efficiency and minimize heat at the kilowatt level. Built on high-gain Silicon LDMOS technology, the system incorporates a dual-directional coupler architecture to monitor critical pulse characteristics using a National Instruments CompactRIO controller. This setup allows for real-time tracking of forward and reflected power via a LabVIEW-based interface, ensuring the amplifier remains stable and within safety limits while delivering the

high-fidelity 63.87 MHz pulses required for superior soft-tissue contrast.

This work details a robust safety interlock circuit and sequencing algorithm designed to protect high-power RFPA systems during 1.5-T MRI operations. The system follows a precise power-up sequence, starting with the drain supply, then the driver gate, and finally the main amplifier gate and RF pulse upon receiving a spectrometer trigger. The final results can be seen in Table 5. To maximize image quality and minimize thermal stress, the Main Amplifier is only active during the RF pulse period, which effectively lowers the noise floor and prevents unnecessary power dissipation. Continuous monitoring of peak current, plate temperature, and VSWR ensures that if any parameter exceeds safe limits, the system immediately triggers a full shutdown of the RF, Gate, and Drain stages, with all real-time health data visualized through an integrated LabVIEW GUI.

IV. CONCLUSION

The ultimate goal of this study is to provide information about radiofrequency power amplifiers, which are the backbone of MRI systems with low or high magnetic fields, and to facilitate research in this area. Various methods and topologies have been examined and explained from a single source. The results of these techniques are also presented using various figures and tables. In addition to

the results, figures of the topologies used have also been included in the study. The evolution of Radio Frequency Power Amplifiers represents a cornerstone in the advancement of Magnetic Resonance Imaging technology. As the “backbone” of the spectrometer, the RFPA is responsible for the precise excitation of nuclear spins, a process that dictates the signal-to-noise ratio, contrast-to-noise ratio, and overall diagnostic utility of the resulting images. This review has synthesized a broad spectrum of research revealing a field in the midst of a significant technological transition. The shift from legacy silicon-based bipolar technologies to wide-bandgap semiconductors and digital control strategies is not merely an incremental improvement; it is a paradigm shift that addresses the dual demands of ultra-high-field performance and portable, low-field accessibility.

One of the findings of this review is the usage of Laterally Diffused Metal Oxide Semiconductor (LDMOS) technology as the contemporary standard for 1.5-T and 3-T systems. LDMOS transistors have demonstrated a unique capability to deliver high peak power with exceptional ruggedness against high Voltage Standing Wave Ratios. This robustness is important in the MRI environment, where load mismatches between the amplifier and the transmit coil are common. However, as the field pushes toward Ultra-High Field imaging, the limitations of silicon are becoming apparent. The emergence of Gallium Nitride and Silicon Carbide offers a path forward. GaN devices provide superior power density and switching speeds, enabling the development of compact, on-coil amplifiers that minimize cable losses and improve B_1^+ field homogeneity in parallel transmit architectures. Meanwhile, SiC is being used in the gradient power amplifier sector, where its high-voltage handling and efficiency allow for the megavolt-ampere levels required for rapid, high-resolution spatial encoding.

Table 6 highlights the diverse performance specifications required across different imaging applications. The data illustrates a wide range of peak power capabilities, from low-power units like the 100 W TOMCO BT01000-Delta designed for high-frequency operation with a 100% duty cycle, to high-power industrial standards like the 18 kW MKS Instruments S35 optimized for 1.5-T systems [28], [75], [76]. Key temporal metrics such as RF rise/fall transition times and pulse-to-edge delays demonstrate the critical trade-off between power magnitude and switching agility. Additionally, the table tracks stringent signal purity and noise requirements, noting that blanking noise levels can be suppressed as low as -171.9 dBm/Hz and harmonic strengths are often held below -40 dBc to preserve the high signal-to-noise ratio essential for diagnostic-quality imaging.

The review also highlights a strategic divergence in amplifier architectures. For clinical 1.5-T and 3-T systems, the Class AB push-pull configuration remains the preferred choice. It offers an optimal compromise between the strict linearity requirements of complex pulse sequences and the efficiency needed to manage thermal loads in a hospital environment. However, the rise of switch-mode power amplifiers,

such as Class D and Class E, represents a disruptive trend for the next generation of MRI. Research into delta-sigma modulation and high oversampling ratios has proven that SMPAs can achieve excitation fidelity comparable to linear amplifiers while operating at significantly higher efficiencies. This efficiency is the primary enabler for portable and ambulance-ready MRI systems, where power budgets and cooling capacities are severely restricted. The transition from viewing the transistor as a controlled current source (linear mode) to a high-speed switch is likely to define the next decade of RFPA research.

Table 7 reveals a broad spectrum of design paradigms tailored for magnetic resonance imaging systems spanning low (0.22 T) to ultra-high (7 T) magnetic field strengths. This table summarizes the papers reviewed in this work. A prominent trend is the extensive utilization of LDMOS and GaN-based semiconductor technologies, frequently operating in Class AB or H-Bridge configurations, to fulfill widely divergent power and frequency demands, ranging from compact 130 W multi-channel modules operating at 1.25 MHz to massive 64 kW architectures driving 210.8 MHz for 5 T systems. Furthermore, the table highlights an operational difference between peak power output and sustained duty cycle capabilities; some topologies, such as the 350 W GaNFET and 1 kW Class AB amplifiers, successfully sustain duty cycles approaching 48–50%, whereas others are generally constrained to 10–20% operational limits. It should be noted that some parameters were not reported in the reviewed studies.

A central theme throughout the middle stages of our review was that “raw power” is useless without “spectral purity.” Because MRI relies on the precise nutation of protons, any distortion in the RF pulse directly translates to ghosting and artifacts in the image. We examined the sophisticated “digital brains” behind these amplifiers, specifically Digital Pre-Distortion (DPD) and Cartesian Feedback. The shift from standard CF to Frequency-Offset Cartesian Feedback (FOCF) represented a major milestone in mitigating DC offsets and quadrature ghosts. These linearization techniques allow engineers to drive transistors closer to their saturation points while using digital algorithms to “clean up” the resulting nonlinearities. This marriage of hardware and software is what allows modern 1.5-T systems to achieve the soft-tissue contrast and resolution we see today.

The physical realization of high-power RF remains a daunting challenge, particularly at lower VHF frequencies where traditional quarter-wave ($\lambda/4$) transmission lines become prohibitively long. The review of passive networks shows a clear trend toward lumped-element Wilkinson and Gysel combiners, as well as the use of high-power coaxial assemblies. While Wilkinson designs offer simplicity and isolation, the Gysel architecture’s grounded isolation resistors provide superior thermal management for 20-kW+ peak power levels. The development of ferrite-based broadband combiners demonstrates that high-performance passive infrastructure can be realized through localized engineering,

reducing reliance on global supply chains while maintaining the high return loss and isolation standards necessary for 1.5-T imaging.

Looking forward, the RFPA landscape is bifurcating into two distinct frontiers: first ultra-high field scaling. As we move toward 11.7-T, the RF wavelength becomes small relative to the human body, leading to destructive interference and “dark spots” in images. The future of RFPA design in this space lies in multi-channel, phase-coherent pTX arrays, where dozens of small, highly efficient GaN amplifiers are synchronized to “shim” the B_1^+ field in real-time. And second, portable low-field systems: The drive for global health equity is fueling research into low-field (0.26-T to 0.5-T) scanners. Here, the challenge is not raw power, but efficiency and cost. The continued refinement of switch-mode Class D architectures and noise-shaping algorithms will be vital in making MRI a ubiquitous tool, accessible even in resource-limited environments.

In conclusion, the modern RFPA is no longer a simple “black box” of amplification but a sophisticated, software-defined power converter. The integration of WBG semiconductors, advanced digital linearization, and robust modular combining strategies has pushed the boundaries of what is possible in medical imaging. As these technologies continue to mature and merge, they will not only enhance the resolution and speed of clinical diagnostics but also redefine the very architecture of the MRI scanner, moving it from a stationary behemoth to a versatile, high-fidelity instrument capable of reaching patients wherever they may be.

REFERENCES

- Y. Wei, C. Yang, H. Jiang, Q. Li, F. Che, S. Wan, S. Yao, F. Gao, T. Zhang, J. Wang, and B. Song, “Multi-nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy: State of the art and future directions,” *Insights Into Imag.*, vol. 13, no. 1, Aug. 2022, pp. 1–17, doi: [10.1186/s13244-022-01262-z](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13244-022-01262-z).
- M. G. Zanchi, P. Stang, A. Kerr, J. M. Pauly, and G. C. Scott, “Frequency-offset Cartesian feedback for MRI power amplifier linearization,” *IEEE Trans. Med. Imag.*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 512–522, Feb. 2011, doi: [10.1109/TMI.2010.2087768](https://doi.org/10.1109/TMI.2010.2087768).
- V. Camarchia, R. Quaglia, A. Piacibello, D. P. Nguyen, H. Wang, and A.-V. Pham, “A review of technologies and design techniques of millimeter-wave power amplifiers,” *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 68, no. 7, pp. 2957–2983, Jul. 2020, doi: [10.1109/TMTT.2020.2989792](https://doi.org/10.1109/TMTT.2020.2989792).
- M. Twieg and M. A. Griswold, “High efficiency radiofrequency power amplifier module for parallel transmit arrays at 3 Tesla,” *Magn. Reson. Med.*, vol. 78, no. 4, pp. 1589–1598, Oct. 2017, doi: [10.1002/mrm.26510](https://doi.org/10.1002/mrm.26510).
- K. B. Weldon and C. A. Olman, “Forging a path to mesoscopic imaging success with ultra-high field functional magnetic resonance imaging,” *Phil. Trans. Roy. Soc. B, Biol. Sci.*, vol. 376, no. 1815, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 20200040, doi: [10.1098/rstb.2020.0040](https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2020.0040).
- J. Chen, Y. Li, Z. Shen, B. Liu, X. Zhang, B. Cao, X. Liu, X. Chu, and H. Zhen, “Design of a high power RF amplifier with configurable number of channels,” in *Proc. ISMRM Annu. Meeting*, 2023, doi: [10.58530/2023/3738](https://doi.org/10.58530/2023/3738).
- L. Wald and E. Adalsteinsson, *Parallel Transmit Technology for High Field MRI*. Erlangen, Germany: MAGNETOM Flash, 2009.
- B. Zhang, K. Wang, and T. Jiang, “RF power design optimization in MRI system,” *Magn. Reson. Lett.*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 89–98, Aug. 2021, doi: [10.1016/j.mrl.2021.100006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mrl.2021.100006).
- N. Sahan, M. E. Inal, S. Demir, and C. Toker, “High-power 20–100-MHz linear and efficient power-amplifier design,” *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 56, no. 9, pp. 2032–2039, Sep. 2008, doi: [10.1109/TMTT.2008.2002238](https://doi.org/10.1109/TMTT.2008.2002238).
- J. Wang, S. Liu, J. Chen, X. Rong, X. Yang, and Y. Li, “8kW non-magnetic RF power amplifier of 5T human body magnetic resonance,” in *Proc. 18th Annu. Conf. China Electrotechnical Soc.*, 2024, pp. 129–140, doi: [10.1007/978-981-97-1428-5_15](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-1428-5_15).
- B. Vachha and S. Y. Huang, “MRI with ultrahigh field strength and high-performance gradients: Challenges and opportunities for clinical neuroimaging at 7 T and beyond,” *Eur. Radiol. Experim.*, vol. 5, no. 1, Aug. 2021, doi: [10.1186/s41747-021-00216-2](https://doi.org/10.1186/s41747-021-00216-2).
- P. A. Bottomley, R. W. Redington, W. A. Edelstein, and J. F. Schenck, “Estimating radiofrequency power deposition in body NMR imaging,” *Magn. Reson. Med.*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 336–349, Aug. 1985, doi: [10.1002/mrm.1910020404](https://doi.org/10.1002/mrm.1910020404).
- C. M. Collins and M. B. Smith, “Signal-to-noise ratio and absorbed power as functions of main magnetic field strength, and definition of ‘90°’ RF pulse for the head in the birdcage coil,” *Magn. Reson. Med.*, vol. 45, no. 4, pp. 684–691, Apr. 2001, doi: [10.1002/mrm.1091](https://doi.org/10.1002/mrm.1091).
- T. S. Ibrahim, “A numerical analysis of radio-frequency power requirements in magnetic resonance imaging experiment,” *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 52, no. 8, pp. 1999–2003, Aug. 2004, doi: [10.1109/TMTT.2004.832021](https://doi.org/10.1109/TMTT.2004.832021).
- S. A. Mohamed, K. Herrmann, A. Adlung, N. Paschke, L. Hausner, L. Frölich, L. Schad, C. Groden, and H. U. Kerl, “Evaluation of sodium (^{23}Na) MR-imaging as a biomarker and predictor for neurodegenerative changes in patients with Alzheimer’s disease,” *Vivo*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 429–435, 2021, doi: [10.21873/invivo.12275](https://doi.org/10.21873/invivo.12275).
- X. Yang, S. Gao, J. Wang, S. Hayat, X. Rong, L. Zou, C. Zou, L. Wan, X. Zhang, H. Zheng, X. Liu, and Y. Li, “A 2-kW high-efficiency and broadband GaN linear RF power amplifier for multinuclear magnetic resonance imaging,” *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 73, no. 9, pp. 6695–6706, Sep. 2025, doi: [10.1109/TMTT.2025.3557471](https://doi.org/10.1109/TMTT.2025.3557471).
- Z. Wen, Y. Xu, Y. Chen, H. Tao, C. Ren, H. Lu, Z. Wang, W. Zheng, B. Zhang, T. Chen, T. Gao, and R. Xu, “A quasi-physical compact large-signal model for AlGaIn/GaN HEMTs,” *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 65, no. 12, pp. 5113–5122, Dec. 2017, doi: [10.1109/TMTT.2017.2765326](https://doi.org/10.1109/TMTT.2017.2765326).
- Y. Xu, C. Wang, H. Sun, Z. Wen, Y. Wu, R. Xu, X. Yu, C. Ren, Z. Wang, B. Zhang, T. Chen, and T. Gao, “A scalable large-signal multi-harmonic model of AlGaIn/GaN HEMTs and its application in C-band high power amplifier MMIC,” *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 65, no. 8, pp. 2836–2846, Aug. 2017, doi: [10.1109/TMTT.2017.2669984](https://doi.org/10.1109/TMTT.2017.2669984).
- A. Fejzuli, R. Kaarsberg, and N. Roldan, “Broadband amplifier gain slope equalization with a single passive component,” *High Freq. Electron.*, vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 22–26, 2006.
- T. Kuang, X. Wang, X. Yin, and Y. Dong, “Design of wide band microstrip equalizer using spurline,” in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Commun. Problem-Solving (ICCP)*, Oct. 2015, pp. 316–318, doi: [10.1109/ICCP.2015.7454161](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCP.2015.7454161).
- S. Zhou and A. K. Jha, “Characteristics modeling of GaN class-AB dual-band PA under different temperature and humidity conditions,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 121632–121644, 2021, doi: [10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3108583](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3108583).
- C. Yu and J. S. Yuan, “Electrical and temperature stress effects on class-AB power amplifier performances,” *IEEE Trans. Electron Devices*, vol. 54, no. 6, pp. 1346–1350, Jun. 2007, doi: [10.1109/TED.2007.896601](https://doi.org/10.1109/TED.2007.896601).
- N. R. Bolding, J. Hannan, C. Vaughn, A. Patel, S. Lin, J. E. P. Sun, W. Grissom, and M. A. Griswold, “A low-cost and compact high-frequency gallium nitride gradient power amplifier for low-field MRI,” *Magn. Reson. Med.*, vol. 95, no. 5, pp. 2992–2999, May 2026, doi: [10.1002/mrm.70221](https://doi.org/10.1002/mrm.70221).
- C. Z. Cooley, P. C. McDaniel, J. P. Stockmann, S. A. Srinivas, S. F. Cauley, M. Śliwiak, C. R. Sappo, C. F. Vaughn, B. Guerin, M. S. Rosen, M. H. Lev, and L. L. Wald, “A portable scanner for magnetic resonance imaging of the brain,” *Nature Biomed. Eng.*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 229–239, Nov. 2020, doi: [10.1038/s41551-020-00641-5](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41551-020-00641-5).
- R. Babaloo and E. Atalar, “Nonlinear droop compensation for current waveforms in MRI gradient systems,” *Magn. Reson. Med.*, vol. 88, no. 2, pp. 973–985, Aug. 2022, doi: [10.1002/mrm.29246](https://doi.org/10.1002/mrm.29246).
- S. A. Winkler, F. Schmitt, H. Landes, J. de Bever, T. Wade, A. Alejski, and B. K. Rutt, “Gradient and shim technologies for ultra high field MRI,” *NeuroImage*, vol. 168, pp. 59–70, Mar. 2018, doi: [10.1016/j.neuroimage.2016.11.033](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2016.11.033).

- [27] T. O'Reilly, W. M. Teeuwisse, D. de Gans, K. Koolstra, and A. G. Webb, "In vivo 3D brain and extremity MRI at 50 mT using a permanent magnet Halbach array," *Magn. Reson. Med.*, vol. 85, no. 1, pp. 495–505, Jan. 2021, doi: [10.1002/mrm.28396](https://doi.org/10.1002/mrm.28396).
- [28] A. R. Purchase, T. Pałasz, H. Sun, J. C. Sharp, and B. Tomanek, "A high duty-cycle, multi-channel, power amplifier for high-resolution radiofrequency encoded magnetic resonance imaging," *Magn. Reson. Mater. Phys., Biol. Med.*, vol. 32, no. 6, pp. 679–692, Dec. 2019, doi: [10.1007/s10334-019-00763-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10334-019-00763-1).
- [29] ZHL-1-2W+ Coaxial amplifier. 50 Ω High Power 2W 5 to 500 MHz, Mini-Circuits. Accessed: Feb. 4, 2026. [Online]. <https://www.minicircuits.com/pdfs/ZHL-1-2W.pdf>
- [30] J. Klitzing. (2016). *A 1 KW SSPA for 1.8-54 MHz. Amateur radio station W6PQL*. Accessed: Jan. 27, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://www.w6pql.com/>
- [31] G. Sarty, S. Kontulainen, A. Baxter-Jones, R. Pierson, K. Turek, A. Obenaus, B. Tomanek, J. Sharp, A. Scott, and L. Piche, "Compact MRI for astronaut physiological research and medical diagnosis," in *Proc. AIAA SPACE Conf. Expo.*, Sep. 2012, doi: [10.2514/6.2012-5240](https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2012-5240).
- [32] A. G. Webb and C. M. Collins, "Parallel transmit and receive technology in high-field magnetic resonance neuroimaging," *Int. J. Imag. Syst. Technol.*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 2–13, Mar. 2010, doi: [10.1002/ima.20219](https://doi.org/10.1002/ima.20219).
- [33] N. Gudino, M. Sonmez, Z. Yao, T. Baig, S. Nielles-Vallespin, A. Z. Faranesh, R. J. Lederman, M. Martens, R. S. Balaban, M. S. Hansen, and M. A. Griswold, "Parallel transmit excitation at 1.5 t based on the minimization of a driving function for device heating," *Med. Phys.*, vol. 42, no. 1, pp. 359–371, Jan. 2015, doi: [10.1118/1.4903894](https://doi.org/10.1118/1.4903894).
- [34] L. Kahn, "Single-sideband transmission by envelope elimination and restoration," *Proc. IRE*, vol. 40, no. 7, pp. 803–806, Jul. 1952, doi: [10.1109/jrproc.1952.273844](https://doi.org/10.1109/jrproc.1952.273844).
- [35] M. Twieg, M. J. Riffe, N. Gudino, and M. A. Griswold, "Enhancement mode GaN (EGaN) FETs for on-coil MRI transmit amplifiers," in *Proc. 21st Sci. Meeting Int. Soc. Magn. Reson. Med.*, 2013.
- [36] J. Wei, C. Liu, Z. Guo, C. Zhou, W. Wang, X. Zhao, J. Zhang, and E. Peng, "Active capacitor voltage balancing control of flying capacitor seven-level soft-switching power amplifiers," *J. Power Electron.*, vol. 26, no. 5, pp. 1039–1053, May 2026, doi: [10.1007/s43236-025-01125-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s43236-025-01125-y).
- [37] H. Obara, T. Ohno, M. Katayama, and A. Kawamura, "Flying-capacitor linear amplifier with capacitor voltage balancing for high-efficiency and low distortion," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 57, no. 1, pp. 614–627, Jan. 2021, doi: [10.1109/TIA.2020.3034560](https://doi.org/10.1109/TIA.2020.3034560).
- [38] A. M. Y. M. Ghias, J. Pou, M. Ciobotaru, and V. G. Agelidis, "Voltage-balancing method using phase-shifted PWM for the flying capacitor multilevel converter," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 29, no. 9, pp. 4521–4531, Sep. 2014, doi: [10.1109/TPEL.2013.2285387](https://doi.org/10.1109/TPEL.2013.2285387).
- [39] G. Kampitsis, E. I. Batzelis, A. Kolokasis, E. Matioli, and B. C. Pal, "A generalized phase-shift PWM extension for improved natural and active balancing of flying capacitor multilevel inverters," *IEEE Open J. Power Electron.*, vol. 3, pp. 621–634, 2022, doi: [10.1109/OJPEL.2022.3209540](https://doi.org/10.1109/OJPEL.2022.3209540).
- [40] F. J. Ortega-Gonzalez, "High power wideband class-E power amplifier," *IEEE Microw. Wireless Compon. Lett.*, vol. 20, no. 10, pp. 569–571, Oct. 2010, doi: [10.1109/LMWC.2010.2064760](https://doi.org/10.1109/LMWC.2010.2064760).
- [41] C. Z. Cooley, J. P. Stockmann, T. Witzel, C. LaPierre, A. Mareyam, F. Jia, M. Zaitsev, Y. Wenhui, W. Zheng, P. Stang, G. Scott, E. Adalsteinsson, J. K. White, and L. L. Wald, "Design and implementation of a low-cost, tabletop MRI scanner for education and research prototyping," *J. Magn. Reson.*, vol. 310, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 106625, doi: [10.1016/j.jmr.2019.106625](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmr.2019.106625).
- [42] A. Malhotra and T. Buzug, "Op-amp based low noise amplifier for magnetic particle spectroscopy," *Current Directions Biomed. Eng.*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 599–602, Sep. 2017, doi: [10.1515/cdbme-2017-0125](https://doi.org/10.1515/cdbme-2017-0125).
- [43] W. Zhang, B. Zheng, P. Goodwill, and S. Conolly, "A custom low-noise preamplifier for magnetic particle imaging," *5th Int. Workshop Magn. Part. Imag. (IWMPPI)*, Istanbul, Türkiye, Mar. 2015, doi: [10.1109/IWMPPI.2015.7107027](https://doi.org/10.1109/IWMPPI.2015.7107027).
- [44] N. Arango, J. P. Stockmann, T. Witzel, L. Wald, and J. White, "Open-source, low-cost, flexible, current feedback-controlled driver circuit for local B0 shim coils and other applications," in *Proc. Int. Soc. Mag. Reson. Med.*, 2016.
- [45] S. Shooshtry and K. Solbach, "Even-odd mode excitation for stability investigation of Cartesian feedback amplifier used in parallel transmit array," in *Proc. 37th Annu. Int. Conf. IEEE Eng. Med. Biol. Soc. (EMBC)*, Aug. 2015, pp. 1572–1575, doi: [10.1109/EMBC.2015.7318673](https://doi.org/10.1109/EMBC.2015.7318673).
- [46] J. Chen, X. Chu, Z. Shen, B. Liu, B. Cao, H. Zhu, X. Zhang, X. Liu, Q. Chen, Y. Li, and H. Zheng, "High-power radio frequency amplifier for 5-T MRI whole-body scanner," *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. 74, pp. 1–11, 2025, doi: [10.1109/TIM.2025.3575994](https://doi.org/10.1109/TIM.2025.3575994).
- [47] X. Chu, X. Yang, Y. Liu, J. Sabate, and Y. Zhu, "Ultra-low output impedance RF power amplifier for parallel excitation," *Magn. Reson. Med.*, vol. 61, no. 4, pp. 952–961, Apr. 2009, doi: [10.1002/mrm.21908](https://doi.org/10.1002/mrm.21908).
- [48] R. Quaglia, J. R. Powell, K. A. Chaudhry, and S. C. Cripps, "Mitigation of load mismatch effects using an orthogonal load modulated balanced amplifier," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 70, no. 6, pp. 3329–3341, Jun. 2022, doi: [10.1109/TMTT.2022.3167414](https://doi.org/10.1109/TMTT.2022.3167414).
- [49] Keysight Technologies, Santa Rosa, CA, USA. *E4991B Impedance Analyzer DataSheet*, Accessed: Mar. 15, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://www.keysight.com/cn/zh/assets/7018-03337/data-sheets/5990-9882.pdf>
- [50] N. Gudino, "Adaptable dual-tuned optically controlled on-coil RF power amplifier for MRI," *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Circuits Syst.*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 165–173, Feb. 2025, doi: [10.1109/TBCAS.2024.3403093](https://doi.org/10.1109/TBCAS.2024.3403093).
- [51] N. Gudino, J. A. Heilman, M. J. Riffe, O. Heid, M. Vester, and M. A. Griswold, "On-coil multiple channel transmit system based on class-D amplification and pre-amplification with current amplitude feedback," *Magn. Reson. Med.*, vol. 70, no. 1, pp. 276–289, Jul. 2013, doi: [10.1002/mrm.24462](https://doi.org/10.1002/mrm.24462).
- [52] L. T. Muftuler, G. Gulsen, K. D. Sezen, and O. Nalcioglu, "Automatic tuned MRI RF coil for multinuclear imaging of small animals at 3T," *J. Magn. Reson.*, vol. 155, no. 1, pp. 39–44, Mar. 2002, doi: [10.1006/jmre.2002.2510](https://doi.org/10.1006/jmre.2002.2510).
- [53] G. A. Keith, C. T. Rodgers, A. T. Hess, C. J. Snyder, J. T. Vaughan, and M. D. Robson, "Automated tuning of an eight-channel cardiac transceive array at 7 Tesla using piezoelectric actuators," *Magn. Reson. Med.*, vol. 73, no. 6, pp. 2390–2397, Jun. 2015, doi: [10.1002/mrm.25356](https://doi.org/10.1002/mrm.25356).
- [54] A. Abuelhajja, K. Solbach, and A. Buck, "Power amplifier for magnetic resonance imaging using unconventional Cartesian feedback loop," in *Proc. German Microw. Conf.*, Mar. 2015, pp. 119–122, doi: [10.1109/GEMIC.2015.7107767](https://doi.org/10.1109/GEMIC.2015.7107767).
- [55] A. Abuelhajja, K. Solbach, and S. Orzada, "Comprehensive study on coupled meandered microstrip line RF coil elements for 7-Tesla magnetic resonance imaging," in *Proc. 9th Eur. Conf. Antennas Propag. (EuCAP)*, Apr. 2015, pp. 1–5.
- [56] D. Ariando, Y. Tang, S. Utsuzawa, Y.-Q. Song, and S. Mandal, "A compact GaN FET-based power amplifier for ASIC-based miniature NMR spectrometers," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Symp. Circuits Syst. (ISCAS)*, May 2021, pp. 1–5, doi: [10.1109/ISCAS51556.2021.9401435](https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCAS51556.2021.9401435).
- [57] D. Ha, J. Paulsen, N. Sun, Y.-Q. Song, and D. Ham, "Scalable NMR spectroscopy with semiconductor chips," *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. USA*, vol. 111, no. 33, pp. 11955–11960, Aug. 2014, doi: [10.1073/pnas.1402015111](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1402015111).
- [58] D. Ariando, C. Chen, M. Greer, and S. Mandal, "An autonomous, highly portable NMR spectrometer based on a low-cost system-on-chip (SoC)," *J. Magn. Reson.*, vol. 299, pp. 74–92, Feb. 2019, doi: [10.1016/j.jmr.2018.12.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmr.2018.12.007).
- [59] D. P. Myer, "Radiofrequency power amplifiers for NMR and MRI," *eMagRes*, vol. 2011, Dec. 2011, doi: [10.1002/9780470034590.emrstm1138](https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470034590.emrstm1138).
- [60] Y. Li, S. Luo, C. Liu, and Y. Ye, "Design and realization of time-domain transfer DPD method for MRI RF power amplifiers," in *Proc. 6th Int. Conf. Electron. Technol. (ICET)*, May 2023, pp. 490–494, doi: [10.1109/icet58434.2023.10211473](https://doi.org/10.1109/icet58434.2023.10211473).
- [61] S. Watanabe, P. Boyagoda, M. Nakaoka, and H. Takano, "Analysis on a PWM power conversion amplifier with IGBT macro model to generate gradient magnetic fields in MRI systems," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Power Electron. Drive Syst. (PEDS)*, Jul. 1999, pp. 127–132, doi: [10.1109/peds.1999.794548](https://doi.org/10.1109/peds.1999.794548).
- [62] H. Yu, K. Liu, and W. Wang, "High-resolution control method for ultra-high-power amplifier in MRI," in *Proc. IEEE PELS Students Young Professionals Symp. (SYPS)*, Aug. 2023, pp. 1–6, doi: [10.1109/syps59767.2023.10268142](https://doi.org/10.1109/syps59767.2023.10268142).
- [63] P. C. Loh, D. G. Holmes, and T. A. Lipo, "Implementation and control of distributed PWM cascaded multilevel inverters with minimal harmonic distortion and common-mode voltage," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 90–99, Jan. 2005, doi: [10.1109/TPEL.2004.839830](https://doi.org/10.1109/TPEL.2004.839830).
- [64] V. D. Boricha, R. A. Jadhav, R. Vishwakarma, T. K. Bhuiya, and R. Harsh, "Power Dividers/Combiners for 1.5T MRI solid state power amplifier," in *Proc. 2nd Int. Conf. Electron., Mater. Eng. Nano-Technol. (IEMENTech)*, May 2018, pp. 1–5, doi: [10.1109/IEMENTECH.2018.8464757](https://doi.org/10.1109/IEMENTECH.2018.8464757).

- [65] E. N. Mohamed, A. G. Sobih, and A. M. El-Tager, "Compact Wilkinson power divider with inductive loaded microstrip line for harmonics suppression," in *Proc. IEEE Middle East Conf. Antennas Propag. (MECAP)*, Sep. 2016, pp. 1–4, doi: [10.1109/MECAP.2016.7790114](https://doi.org/10.1109/MECAP.2016.7790114).
- [66] M. Ehses, M. Prier, B. Mydla, and H. Maune, "Effect of different oversampling ratios for switch mode amplifiers in low-field magnetic resonance imaging *," in *Proc. 47th Annu. Int. Conf. IEEE Eng. Med. Biol. Soc. (EMBC)*, Jul. 2025, pp. 1–4, doi: [10.1109/embc58623.2025.11254020](https://doi.org/10.1109/embc58623.2025.11254020).
- [67] ((2024)). *Ocra: The Open-Source Console for Realtime Acquisitions. Visited: 09*. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/OpenMRI/ocra>
- [68] T. K. Bhuiya, B. Naik, and R. Harsh, "Indigenous development of 15kW RF power amplifier for 1.5T MRI scanner," in *Proc. IEEE Microw. Antennas, Propag. Conf. (MAPCON)*, Dec. 2023, pp. 1–5, doi: [10.1109/mapcon58678.2023.10464134](https://doi.org/10.1109/mapcon58678.2023.10464134).
- [69] K. Nerurkar, P. Mane, T. K. Bhuiya, V. Padwal, and R. Harsh, "RF exciter control system for head imaging in 1.5t MRI," in *IEEE MTT-S Int. Microw. Symp. Dig.*, Dec. 2021, pp. 1–4, doi: [10.1109/marc49196.2021.9714690](https://doi.org/10.1109/marc49196.2021.9714690).
- [70] S. C. Cripps, "RF power amplifiers for wireless communications," *IEEE Microw. Mag.*, vol. 1, no. 1, p. 64, Mar. 2000, doi: [10.1109/MMW.2000.823830](https://doi.org/10.1109/MMW.2000.823830).
- [71] *AN8110 RF Amplifier Installation Manual. Analogic Corporation Medical Imaging Division, Insert no 16-00070, REV. 02., Binder, no 28-002011, Publication, no 10-62836-01, ANALOGIC: The World Resource for Health and Security Technology, Geneva, Switzerland, 2002.*
- [72] *500 W Pulsed RF Amplifier Model BT00 BETA Operation Manual, document T001591 Issue A, Tomco Electronics Pty Ltd, TOMCO Technologies, Jun. 2002.*
- [73] Communication Power Corporation (CPC). (2012). *The World's Leading Supplier of Broadband Power Amplifiers*. Model 0.2T500M. Accessed: Feb. 5, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cpcamps.com/wp-content/sheets/0.2T500M.pdf>
- [74] M. Harrington, W. Heist, C. Loriatti, and J. White. (N/A) *Product Specification Document XX-S35-64. 18 kW, 1.5T Linear, Solid State RF Pulse*. Accessed: Feb. 5, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mksinst.com/f/63-87-mhz-mri-rf-amplifier>
- [75] Tomco Technologies (2019). *RF Amplifier Data Sheet BT01000-Delta*. Accessed: Feb. 5, 2026. [Online]. Available: https://www.tomcorf.com/assets/standard_pulsed/DS006689H.pdf
- [76] *Ultra Electronics Herley (N/A) RF Power Amplifier System Model 3900-1. 3061*. Lancaster, PA, USA. Accessed: Feb. 5, 2026. [Online]. Available: <http://www.bptec.com/pdf/AMT/3900C-12%2009-30-02.pdf>
- [77] *ANALOGIC: The World Resource for Health and Security Technology (2016) 6 kW RF Power Amplifier for MRI Scanner Applications, Analogic Medical Imaging Group.*, document ANALOGIC Corporation, Bulletin 16-00115, REV 1 3/04, Printed in USA, 2016.

OĞUZHAN KIZILBEY received the B.Sc., M.Sc., and Ph.D. degrees in electronics engineering from Istanbul Technical University (ITU), Istanbul, Türkiye, in 2005, 2008, and 2012, respectively. His M.Sc. research focused on X-band dielectric resonator oscillators, and his Ph.D. work introduced a new approach to high-efficiency Class-E balanced power amplifier design, culminating in the development of a GaN-based balanced PA operating at 3.5–3.8 GHz with 20-W output power and 75% efficiency. He was an Associate Professor with the Interuniversity Council, in 2014. From 2005 to 2017, he was with TÜBİTAK BİLGEM, as a Researcher contributing to national RF and microwave system developments. Since 2017, he has been with the TÜBİTAK National Metrology Institute (TÜBİTAK UME), where he is currently a Senior Chief Researcher. Since 2024, he has also been a part-time Faculty Member with ITU. He has authored more than 50 publications, holds two national patents. His current work spans high-power RF/microwave transmitter subsystems, RF power metrology and calibration, and RF hardware for medical and industrial applications, including low-field MRI instrumentation, where he is involved in the design of a 1-kW, 10-MHz RF power amplifier and a gradient amplifier subsystem. He serves as a Reviewer for multiple IEEE journals, including IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON MICROWAVE THEORY AND TECHNIQUES and IEEE ACCESS.

BAKİ KARABÖCE has been with the TÜBİTAK National Metrology Institute (TÜBİTAK UME), since 1993. He is an expert in acoustic, vibration, ultrasonic, electrical, mechanical, and medical measurements. He is the Founder and the Director of the Medical Metrology Research Laboratory. He is the Coordinator of the Metrology for Medical Electrical Devices Project under the European Program for Metrology (EPM) health call of the European Association of Metrology

Centres (EURAMET). He is also the proposer and member of the Health Working Group established within EURAMET, actively participating in the organization, programming, and strategy development of all projects. He is the Turkish representative of the EURAMET TC-AUV (Acoustics, Ultrasonics, and Vibration) Ultrasonic section and a member of the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) TC87 Ultrasonic group. He has participated in and completed six projects under the 7th Framework Program and Horizon 2020 programs. He has served as an editor for scientific journals, authored numerous book chapters at national and international levels, acted as a reviewer for conferences and journals, and published a large number of scientific papers. He is a member of the IEEE Medical Measurements and Applications (MeMeA) board of directors. He serves as a reviewer and consultant for TÜBİTAK TARAL (national funding) projects. He has chaired international conferences (IEEE MeMeA Istanbul, in 2019) and organized sessions. He has served as the president of the Turkish Acoustics Association.

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MERT KARADEMİR received the B.S. degree in electrical and electronics engineering from the Faculty of Engineering and Natural Sciences, Bahçeşehir University, Istanbul, Türkiye, in 2024. He is currently pursuing the M.S. degree in electronics engineering from Istanbul Technical University, Istanbul. He is a Part-Timer with Türkiye Bilimsel ve Teknolojik Araştırma Kurumu (TÜBİTAK), Kocaeli, Türkiye, where this study has been funded. He had two internship experiences at Havelan Teknoloji Radar, Ankara, and Aselsan, Ankara, respectively.